

D7.6 TRANSFORM: an Assessment of Outcomes and Impacts

TRANSFORM

Deliverable description

Deliverable:

D7.6 TRANSFORM: an Assessment of Outcomes and Impacts

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Summary for Policymakers

TRANSFORM is a coordination and support action funded under the SwafS-14 call topic of Horizon 2020 to help implement the principles and practices of RRI – Responsible Research and Innovation – into institutions, policies, and practices of innovation at the regional scale. To this effect, the project involves itself in processes of innovation, policymaking, and practice in three European regions: Lombardy, Catalonia and the Brussels-Capital region, our so-called “clusters”. The project initiatives include efforts to introduce RRI approaches into S3 policies in the three regions.

This deliverable, D7.6, contains the core chapters of a scientific publication that will be finally submitted in February 2023 (open access academic book to be published in 2023 by Routledge) that is a full-length in-depth study of TRANSFORM. The book will be published on paper and as open access, freely downloadable e-book with Creative Commons BY-NC-ND license. It is provisionally titled *Innovation Governance in Three European Regions: Translations of Responsibility*, and is a co-authored monography by Thomas Völker, Rasmus Slaattelid and Roger Strand, all at the University of Bergen.

The main finding of D7.6 is the same as that of D7.4 and D7.5, though documented and analysed in much greater detail: the importance of what we call "often-invisible work" of establishing, nurturing, and caring for relationships conducive of RRI at the local/regional level. Most of such work, which can be of critical importance to the success of RRI initiatives, is hardly visible if one tries to quantify or otherwise capture it by existing RRI indicators. This is why we – in line with the general recent developments of this academic field the latter years – adopted and further developed the qualitative research methodology of evaluative inquiry, as explained in D7.5.

An important observation is that most of such work, which can be of critical importance to the success of RRI initiatives, is hardly visible if one tries to quantify or otherwise capture it by existing RRI indicators. Our study documents the presence of such work in all three regions of TRANSFORM and explains how the pilots in all three regions are on pathways to achieving impact and, from an RRI perspective, benefit for society.

At the same time, the TRANSFORM Grant Agreement mentioned a set of MoRRI indicators (GE1, GE3, SLSE4, PE5, PE6, PE7, PE8 and GOV2) to which TRANSFORM might contribute, that is, for which TRANSFORM activities might have had outcomes and impacts that contribute to improving the states of affairs that the indicators were supposed to measure or at least be some kind of proxies for.

Starting with the Gender Equality indicators GE1 and GE3, these refer to the share of RPOs and RFOs, respectively, with gender equality plans. If we take them as proxies for the state of affairs of gender equality in the E&I ecosystem more generally, we may point to at least two contributions by TRANSFORM. First, in a very direct sense, the endometriosis pilot in Catalonia has contributed to gender equality by being a citizen science pilot that engaged and mobilised women with a much-ignored health condition and thereby improved the gender aspects of the content of research. Secondly, in a more indirect way, TRANSFORM may have contributed to gender equality by means of exemplary learning in the respective clusters, in that all three cluster leaders and the vast majority of persons-in-charge of project partners are female.

The SLSE4 indicator is a proxy for the presence of citizen science in RPOs. Taken more broadly, TRANSFORM has contributed to increase the presence and importance of citizen science in the Catalan R&I ecosystem, not only in traditional RPOs but more specifically by citizen science becoming introduced in the RIS3CAT2030 strategy.

PE5-PE8 are all indicators of public engagement. PE5 is a measure of public engagement mechanisms in RPOs; PE7 embedment of PE in RFOs; and PE8 PE in evaluation criteria in research proposal evaluation. TRANSFORM has definitely contributed to the underlying state of affairs for PE5, PE7 and PE8. For instance, the pilots at UC Louvain introduced PE mechanisms in an RPO (PE5). All three clusters contributed to embedding PE in the regional S3 authorities (which can be taken to be “RFOs” in this context, thus contributing to PE7). And while the precise change of evaluation criteria did not take place during the lifetime of TRANSFORM, this was indeed one of the long-term ambitions shaping the work of the Brussels cluster (PE8).

Finally, GOV2 is a proxy for the presence of RRI-related governance mechanisms. Both in Lombardy and Catalonia, RRI was indeed embedded in practice and policy in the regional authorities during TRANSFORM (and then we already discussed above the methodological difficulties of causal attribution), and positive developments were also observed in the Brussels Capital Region.

It may be interesting to compare TRANSFORM contributions with the main process indicators that were recommended by the EC expert group (Strand et al. 2015, Table 3.1):

	Process indicators
Public engagement	Number and degree of development of formal procedures for citizens' involvement (consensus conferences, referendum, etc.) Number of citizen science projects, discriminating from those supported by institutions and those that are created at grassroots level, by field
Gender equality	Percentage of research institutions that document specific actions that aim to change aspects of their organisational culture that reinforces gender bias
Science education	The inclusion of an initiative or requirement for RRI-related training in a research strategy/call/work programme, etc. (yes/no, percentage)
Open access	Inclusion of open science measures in research policies and calls for proposals
Ethics	Documented ELSI/ELSA project component and/or transdisciplinary component that addresses societal relevance and ethical acceptability (presence/frequency; qualitative descriptions; best practices)
Governance	Identification of formal and informal networks of R & I that promote RRI, at both the national and the EU level

Indeed, these qualitative process indicators for public engagement, gender equality, ethics and governance are better suited to characterize the positive contributions of TRANSFORM. The project developed and implemented formal procedures for citizens' involvement in all three regions; it worked on the gender bias of the organisational culture in one Catalan pilot; it introduced transdisciplinary components that addressed societal relevance in all three regions; and it most definitely worked on maintaining, nurturing, and fostering formal and informal networks that promote RRI in the three regions.

To sum up, in our assessment, TRANSFORM had significant positive outcomes and are likely to have had significant positive impact in line with the SwafS call and the Grant Agreement.

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Introduction to this Deliverable

TRANSFORM is a coordination and support action funded under the SwafS-14 call topic of Horizon 2020 to help implement the principles and practices of RRI – Responsible Research and Innovation – into institutions, policies, and practices of innovation at the regional scale. To this effect, the project involves itself in processes of innovation, policymaking, and practice in three European regions: Lombardy, Catalonia and the Brussels-Capital region, our so-called “clusters”. The project initiatives include efforts to introduce RRI approaches into S3 policies in the three regions.

The TRANSFORM project includes a separate work package, WP7, dedicated to monitoring and evaluation of project activities and results during project lifetime. This deliverable, D7.6, corresponds to TRANSFORM Task 7.4, “RRI assessment of the activities and outcomes of TRANSFORM”. We have performed this task in line with the Grant Agreement, which states that it: “... is the one that will take the highest degree of methodological distance to the project and it will be performed by UiB only, consulting with the Advisory Board of the project.”

The main finding of D7.6 is the same as that of D7.4 and D7.5, though documented and analysed in much greater detail: the importance of what we call “often-invisible work” of establishing, nurturing and caring for relationships conducive of RRI at the local/regional level. Most of such work, which can be of critical importance to the success of RRI initiatives, is hardly visible if one tries to quantify or otherwise capture it by existing RRI indicators. This is why we – in line with the general recent developments of this academic field the latter years – adopted and further developed the qualitative research methodology of evaluative inquiry, as explained in D7.5.

The choice in the Grant Agreement of making TRANSFORM Deliverable D7.6 a scientific publication that presents original research, has the advantage of increasing the dissemination level and potentially the impact of the results. The potential disadvantage is that scientific publications have a genre that can be hard to access for non-specialists. This is perhaps even more true for D7.6 than D7.4 and D7.5, because the D7.6 is an academic book with a length of >100 pages. For this reason, as stated before, we have decided to use the results also to prepare a voluntary update of D7.3 into a Second Version, to submitted as soon as possible.

This deliverable is public. However, the scientific manuscript is not yet submitted and peer reviewed. While being in the process of peer review, and while being in the process of approval qua project deliverable, we will follow academic convention and not disseminate it actively. If the project deliverable is approved before the book is in print, we will follow academic convention and upload and disseminate a preprint, submission version (indeed being this deliverable document).

We now proceed to describe the contents of this deliverable. The University of Bergen team (represented by Thomas Völker, Rasmus Slaattelid and Roger Strand) has signed a book contract with Routledge, a well-reputed academic publisher within the Taylor & Francis Group. The full manuscript is due 28 February 2023, two months later than the final TRANSFORM deliverable called D7.6. This ensures that the latest updates, including information from the final conference of TRANSFORM, can be included in the analysis of this arguable most ambitious scientific deliverable from WP7.

In 2023, we will submit updates of D7.6:

- Early March 2023, when the full manuscript is submitted, and
- Towards the end of 2023, when the book is scheduled to be published.

The book will be published on paper and as open access, freely downloadable e-book with Creative Commons BY-NC-ND license. It is provisionally titled:

Innovation Governance in Three European Regions: Translations of Responsibility

The full book will include several chapters that explain the context of RRI and Science-with-and-for-Society as well as discuss TRANSFORM results in a broader context of innovation governance. We believe that these chapters also will be interesting and relevant for policy work in DG RTD, DG REGIO, and possibly other parts of the European Commission. However, they go beyond the mere assessment of TRANSFORM outcomes and impacts which is the topic of D7.6. We have therefore prioritized work on the four chapters that are most relevant for D7.6 now in 2022, one chapter for each of the TRANSFORM clusters and one chapter that performs a comparison between them. This corresponds to Section II, chapters 4-7, of the outline presented below. We will finalize the rest of the manuscript in January-February 2023 (at in-kind cost since the Grant Agreement period expires 31 Dec 2022). In what follows, we present the book outline, then each of the four mentioned chapters, and finally, a short conclusion.

The Book Outline

T. Völker, R. Slaattelid & R. Strand: Innovation Governance in Three European Regions: Translations of Responsibility will be a book in the Routledge Series “History and Philosophy of Technoscience”. It will have 10 chapters and a length around 100-150,000 words.

Themes and objectives of the book: A central motif in the governance of technoscience is the desire for what in EU jargon has come to be called “better alignment” between the research and innovation sector and greater society, sometimes construed as “civil society” or “the needs and concerns of the citizens”. In current R&I policy in the European Union this desire materialized into policy concepts such as “Responsible Research and Innovation”, or RRI.

This book situates RRI in the broader context of governance of technoscience and presents original empirical studies of attempts to “do RRI” by integrating RRI into the regional R&I policies of three European regions: the Brussels-Capital region, Lombardy, and Catalonia. While all three regions are known to be strong in terms of science, technology, and industry, we show the vast distance (in several dimensions) between top-down conceptions of governance in the EU and the governance practices within R&I ecosystems at the local and regional level. If judged as a top-down “implementation” of a predefined vision of RRI, these efforts may appear as failures, in the sense that the predefined vision is not reflected in the evidence. However, throughout our studies we show that it is better to analyse such efforts as *translations* of RRI across levels and domains rather than “implementation”. Responsibility and the desire for better alignment is translated and enacted in transformative ways and with surprising purposes. The book draws two sets of lessons from these experiences: First, that there is more governance of technoscience than one may think, and secondly, that there is a need to rethink the borders of technoscience and where it resides.

Submitted abstract: In 2020, the EU-funded TRANSFORM project set out to integrate the principle of Responsible Research and Innovation – RRI – into the research and innovation policies of three European regions: Lombardy, Brussels, and Catalonia. This book tells the stories of TRANSFORM and the multiple translations of the RRI principle on its way from philosophy of technology to EU policy jargon, further to EU work programs and calls for action and finally into the real-life practices and events in these regions. These stories

show how responsibility is translated in creative ways, with surprising goals and ambiguous outcomes. Armed with these stories, the book analyses the broader context of the desire for better governance of technoscience and draws two sets of lessons: First, that there is more governance of technoscience than one may think, and secondly, that there is a need to rethink the borders of technoscience and the spaces in which it resides.

Synopsis

Section I – Introduction

The first section of the book is devoted to providing the basis for the subsequent sections. It does so in three steps: first, it outlines the specific problem this book will address. Second, it describes the conceptual lenses that are applied to address this problem, and third, it gives an overview of the broader debates both in policy and academia to which we want to contribute.

Chapter 1 – The problem of responsibility in the governance of technoscience

The opening chapter of the book describes the responsible research and innovation movement as one moment in an ongoing struggle over adequate modes of governing technoscience. As such it resonates with and takes up debates about the democratization of science and technology, citizen participation and engagement and, more broadly, experiments with deliberative democracy. From this starting point the chapter will argue that it is by looking at the concrete sites of such experiments with the governance of technoscience that we gain a more nuanced understanding of the local practices of responsible research and innovation and about the networks that provide the conditions for responsibility.

Chapter 2 – Conceptual approach of the book

The second chapter of the book details our understanding of RRI in the context of the governance of technoscience. We will detail our understanding through developing the notion of “translation” and bring it together with literatures on responsible research and innovation and on ecologies of participation, which will allow us to pay particular attention to the collectives, carriers, and mediators that both stabilize and co-emerge with particular translations of responsibility. Translation in this way will be developed as a way to talk more productively about processes of implementation and about the shifts and

transformations that occur when abstract ideas are travelling across levels and scales and turn into localized practices.

Chapter 3 – Translating responsibility into RRI and Science-with-and-for-Society (SwafS)

To deepen this description of our understanding of RRI it is additionally necessary to show how this term emerged together with a very distinct funding environment: the SwafS project calls of the broader Horizon 2020 research framework programme of the European Union. Chapter three thus provides an overview of the emergence, stabilization, and potential decline of RRI both as a policy term and as a concept within academic literature. In doing so the chapter will also point to the predecessors and lineage of the term and to its possible legacy. The chapter will also prepare the ground for the next section by showing translations of responsibility from the SwafS programme, via a funding call, to what ultimately became the umbrella project for the cases to be presented in Section II.

Section II – Territorial translations of the responsible governance of research and innovation

The second section provides an in-depth empirical look at case studies in which the concept of RRI gets translated into territorial R&I projects under the umbrella of a SwafS¹⁴ project. These case studies will then be compared to each other and contrasted with a Norwegian RRI initiative.

Chapter 4 – Institutionalizing deliberative democracy in Lombardy

The first of the empirical chapters describes an initiative to design and conduct a participatory agenda setting process and an attempt to set-up a citizen assembly on Artificial Intelligence in Lombardy. These activities are steps in the broader objective of Fondazione Giannino Bassetti to institutionalize principles and methods of deliberative democracy and to anchor them in Lombardian research and innovation governance.

Chapter 5 – Citizen science as innovation governance in Catalonia

Following that, we will travel to Barcelona to explore two projects in which approaches from the citizen science movement are brought into conversation with the aims of responsible research and innovation. Two very different technoscientific issues are addressed here: endometriosis and waste collection practices. Distinct as they may seem, these issues tell important stories about how certain networks are established to deal with these issues in a responsive and reflexive manner.

Chapter 6 – Regional development and co-design in the Brussels-Capital region

The final case study details attempts to institutionalize RRI practices in the Brussels-capital region. RRI is translated here as regional development through co-creation and co-design. This is done by engaging actors around technoscientific issues such as water quality measurement and food waste. Additionally, this chapter describes attempts to reshape the evaluation schemes and practices of a local research and innovation funding agency.

Chapter 7 – Comparison – Translations, carriers, and mediators

Chapter 7 provides an in-between conclusion in the shape of a project-internal comparison of three cases by asking how RRI gets translated in each of the three distinct R&I ecosystems and by telling a story about how both RRI and the regional RRI ecosystem get enacted in specific ways. This is done by looking especially at how the different ecosystems enable certain activities while making others more difficult, thus acting as carriers and mediators while being themselves re-shaped in subtle ways.

Chapter 8 – A sideview to the laboratory

In addition to the internal comparative lens, we will contrast the three case studies with a Norwegian RRI initiative: the Centre for Digital Life Norway, which aims at re-thinking science-intensive biotechnology in Norway according to the principle of responsible research and innovation realized through transdisciplinary collaboration.

Section III – Conclusions

The final section makes use of the insights from the empirical chapter to take up the questions and challenges articulated in section I. It does so by unpacking conceptions about the responsible governance of technoscience.

Chapter 9 – What happened to the governance of technoscience?

The first of the concluding chapters aims at bringing together the debates from the policy realm with the academic literature on RRI and our empirical analysis to ask for the models of governance that become visible in the translations of responsibility and how these models are mutually constitutive with the carriers and mediators through which they are temporally stabilized. In this way the chapter shows how there is more governance of technoscience than one may think.

Chapter 10 – What happened to the technoscience to be governed?

The second chapter of this concluding section is devoted to the notion of technoscience itself and will use the empirical case studies to discuss the multiple versions of technoscience that are enacted in the translation of responsibility. In doing so it directs attention to the need to rethink both the borders of technoscience and collectively held ideas about where it resides.

The University of Bergen has been the partner responsible for the preparation of the deliverable. We are grateful for the advice from our Advisory Board.

We now move to the four chapters that assess outcomes and (to the extent possible before the very end of the project) impacts of TRANSFORM.

Chapter 4 – Institutionalizing deliberative democracy in Lombardy

Of bookshelves and wooden tables

It is December 2021, and we are about to meet our Lombardian project partners in-person for the first time after nearly two years of online project meetings. When we arrive at Milano Centrale - the main train station - we realize that the city is already in full-on Christmas mode. The streets and the myriad shops are decorated with beautiful festive lights. Fondazione Giannino Bassetti (FGB), where we will meet our colleagues, is in walking distance, so we decide to use the opportunity for a little walk through the city. We pass old buildings until we arrive at Porta Venezia, also fully decorated with Christmas lights. We cross the street, trying not to become a casualty of Italian traffic and are now almost there.

Arriving at the offices of FGB we are immediately impressed with the ceiling-high wooden bookshelves that cover the walls of the meeting room and are full of volumes on science, innovation, and society. We are offered an espresso - thank you Lombardian hospitality - and get a little tour through the offices. The rooms of the Fondazione are clearly designed for lectures and debates. We are especially in awe of a huge wooden table and accompanying lustre in one of the rooms, which look like as if the building was built around them.

The building and FGB offices clearly embody the history and standing of FGB within the Lombardian research and innovation ecosystem as an arbiter of dialogue and debate of issues of responsibility. The particular translation of RRI in the TRANSFORM project, to be unpacked on this chapter, can only be understood properly when taking these dimensions into account.

Participatory agenda setting and citizens' juries – towards deliberative democracy

"The citizenry is quite capable of sound deliberation. But deliberative democratization will not just happen." (Dryzek et al., 2019)

Over the recent years there has been a renewed interest in different forms of deliberative democracy both in academia and beyond. Inter- and supra-national bodies like the OECD or the European Commission have strengthened their efforts to develop and institutionalize novel forms of citizen participation in policy- and decision-making.

In its highly influential report “Innovative Citizen Participation in New Democratic Institutions – Catching the Deliberative Wave” from 2020 (OECD, 2020) representative deliberative processes are presented as a way to address the growing complexity of policy-making in the context of the pressing societal challenges of our time. The “ordinary citizen” is having a triumphant return as a central figure in policy- and decision-making. As a collection of case studies this report understands itself as a guide to policy-makers who are interested in establishing and institutionalizing forms of deliberation within mechanisms and procedures. Drawing on a long lineage of scholarship on the topic, the OECD describes three main principles of citizen participation and engagement: deliberation as the careful discussion of certain issues based on information and evidence, representativeness based on random sampling, and impact in the sense of a link to decision-making processes. Following up on this report the OECD also published evaluation guidelines for deliberative processes (OECD, 2021). In these guidelines, five core principles for evaluating initiatives of citizen engagement and participation are spelt out: independence, transparency, being evidence-based, accessibility, and constructiveness.

The growing importance of engagement and deliberation on a policy level is also illustrated by the launch of the so-called “Competence Centre on Participatory and Deliberative Democracy (CC DEMOS)”. The establishment of this Centre is arguably a step towards institutionalizing forms of experimenting with different modes of governance. The self-understanding of CC DEMOS is to “support” policy-making. It does so through a number of activities, including capacity building as well as designing and conducting different forms of citizen engagement. The establishment of such an institution within the European Commission might signal a cultural shift towards more participatory forms of policy- and decision making. A recent report by Alberto Alemanno (2022), commissioned by the

European Parliament's Committee on Constitutional Affairs, is further indication of such a shift. In this study Alemanno argues for the establishment of permanent deliberative mechanisms – focusing on randomly selected EU citizens - in EU institutions. Reports like this one are part of a broader discussion on the role deliberative mechanisms can (and should) legitimately have within policy- and decision-making processes at the European level.

These attempts of re-shaping European democratic institutions can be traced back (at least) to the White Paper on European governance (COM(2001) 428) where participation was listed as one of five core principles of European governance. The other principles are openness, accountability, effectiveness and coherence being the other four. As understood in this document, participation is envisioned to improve the relevance, effectiveness and thus overall quality of EU policies through increased opportunities for participation throughout the whole policy cycle.

When we look beyond the policy realm, it becomes clear that the idea of deliberative democracy is in fact quite old - some even trace it back all the way to Aristotle (Dryzek et al., 2019). Different versions of what is currently subsumed under the umbrella terms “deliberative forums” (Niemeyer, 2011) or “mini-publics” (Goodin & Dryzek, 2006; Grönlund et al., 2014) actually have quite a long history. They initially emerged in the 1970s as citizen juries and planning cells (J. P. Voß & Amelung, 2016) before they were further developed at the Jefferson Center in the 1970s, and then took the form of so-called “consensus conferences” in Denmark through the Danish Board of Technology. The board has a fairly unique position as it was institutionalized as a public body to support the Danish parliament. As such it has been a hub for research and development of public participation approaches and procedures (J. P. Voß & Amelung, 2016). Courant (2021) distinguishes six generations of deliberative mini-publics: the starting point in his genealogy is the French High Council of the Military Function, a mini-public responsible for dealing with different matters regarding soldiers' working conditions. The next generation in his list is the Citizen's Juries and Planning cells methods that were established in the 1970ies and used to draft reports in support of policy processes. He then proceeds to the Consensus Conferences of the Danish Board of Technology in the 80s, and further to the method of Deliberative Polling that was initiated in the 90s – a method that introduced the difference between “considered” and “raw” opinions (Mansbridge, 2010). Before arriving at the Citizens' Assembly approach, he mentions the Oregon Citizens' Initiative Review (established in 2010), a panel that produces information on upcoming referendums.

While different approaches to citizen engagement often have characteristics that sets them apart from one another, we should nevertheless recognize their difference: they often bring together a representative sample of citizens from a certain constituency, usually via randomized sampling; they are organized around procedures for reasoned debate and deliberation; and finally, they produce recommendations that are expected to impact policy- and decision making. Usually, these processes are guided by professional facilitators. During the process citizens are provided with information by experts before they discuss and develop recommendations on the issues at hand. The idea is that the outcome of these deliberations are consensual judgements of recommendations.

The size of such mini-publics can vary substantially: there are citizens' juries which convene groups of 10-25 citizens, then there are initiatives that bring together around 150 people to deliberate, and for the big constitutional initiatives up to 900 citizens were involved. Referring to these bigger and more impactful initiatives scholars are diagnosing (or announcing) a "constitutional turn" (Suiter & Reuchamps, 2016) for deliberative democracy.

Research has shown that citizens are willing to participate in meaningful forms of public engagement and that, if the process is well organized, they are perfectly capable of contributing to high-level deliberations. Furthermore, the focus on thinking together can help overcome tendencies of polarization, as deliberation promotes considered collective judgement (Dryzek et al., 2019). This then relates to one of the most crucial common elements of deliberative mini-publics, brilliantly summarized by Dryzek et al. in their piece in the journal *Science*:

"The science of deliberative democracy seeks evidence on the capacities of citizens as they engage democratic dialogue, not as they respond as isolated individuals to survey questions (or even as they respond in social psychological experiments that fail to capture key democratic features)." (Dryzek et al., 2019)

Such forms of engagement are about collective reasoning and thus imply a particular vision of what an "opinion" is, in contrast to visions of what an "opinion" is in normal polling. Whereas polling implicitly or explicitly assumes that an opinion is held by an actor and can simply be "extracted" by means of a survey, deliberative formats, on the other hand, pay tribute to the more dynamic nature of opinion formation. Such formats can therefore allow for opinions to shift and change when confronted with reasoned arguments.

There is one important distinction between citizens' juries and other forms of deliberative mini-publics: They can either be "state-supported" or "civil-society-led" (Courant, 2021). This

distinction points to the fact that it does inevitably make a difference whether citizen's assemblies are organized top down or if they emerge bottom-up through the initiative of citizens or civil society organizations. Whereas the former start from an official mandate, are well-funded and thus able to organize deliberations over a longer period of time, the latter enjoy less institutional support and relies on crowd-funding or sponsoring. In fact, because the latter are more attuned to the actual issues citizens face, they are occasionally turned into state-supported citizens' assemblies. An example of this is the Irish Constitutional Convention and subsequent citizens' assemblies.

The distinction between state-supported and civil-society-led forms of deliberative democracy resonates with a distinction that is more common in the field of science and technology studies (STS) – the distinction between “invited” and uninvited” participation (Wynne, 2007, 2011). This distinction addresses similar issues to the one we just discussed but accentuates different aspects of it. Whereas Courants points to the benefits of having state-support in terms of mandate and resources, Wynne is more interested in issues of boundary-drawing, inclusion, and exclusion. He argues that being the one “inviting” others and engaging them goes beyond questions of procedure and material resources, since it allows for creating the ways in which citizens are engaged and their room for manoeuvre. This is usually done by creating the subject-identities and repertoires for action that participants can then fill in. Being invited, then, always entails being invited in a certain capacity to do certain things (and not others). Having the power to define these things before the deliberation even begins, so the argument goes, creates a power asymmetry that even the best and fairest procedure can not compensate for. Wynne asks: “How are implicit boundaries of public agency and involvement thus set and enforced in the very discursive-practical routines which are allowed to define such supposedly inclusive processes?” (Wynne, 2007, p. 104)

Questions like this resonate with the challenges and concerns deliberative mini-publics are facing. Such concerns relate to implicit assumptions about the participants of public deliberations (Michael, 2012; Soneryd & Amelung, 2016). As stressed by Wynne and others (Goven, 2006; Irwin, 2006; Lezaun & Soneryd, 2007), neither “the public” nor “the citizen” are fixed or neutral categories. They usually come with expectations about who citizens are and how they should ideally behave. Also “publics” are often treated as static entities that exist independently of certain political issue. Research on participation and engagement, however, shows that the initiatives themselves contribute to creating the publics they pretend to engage (Felt & Fochler, 2010). Importantly, there is a drive towards consensus

formation and thus different procedures associated with deliberative democracy show a tendency to repress differences (Horst & Irwin, 2010), which is why scholars have referred to them as “machineries for manufacturing consensus (Felt & Fochler, 2010).

Given these insights from the debate on different modes and formats of deliberative democracy, there is a definitive need to constantly reflect on the institutionally stabilized assumptions about the roles assigned to the participants, as well as how the choice of certain approaches over others will impact power asymmetries and thus possible outcomes of the deliberations.

So, while there is ample evidence that citizens are indeed perfectly capable of contributing to democratic policy- and decision-making, there are also numerous empirical studies that point to practical as well as systemic barriers that might hinder meaningful integration of citizens into political processes. That’s why we chose this particular introductory quote: citizens are perfectly capable of making meaningful contributions to political processes on many levels and throughout all phases of the policy cycle. The question is whether they are allowed to contribute. Deliberative democracy does not just happen by itself. The story we want to tell about the Lombardian pilot activities within the Transform project address exactly this issue: what needs to be done to make deliberative democracy appealing to regional administrations and this possible in the long-run?

Showcasing participatory agenda setting and citizens’ juries

The Lombardy cluster activities consisted of a combination of a participatory research agenda setting process on just energy transitions and a citizens’ jury devoted to the issue of smart mobility. These activities were designed and conducted by Fondazione Giannino Bassetti (FGB) and their partners from the regional administration, Region Lombardia and Finlombarda. The goal of these participatory activities as presented on the project website was “to render S3 more inclusive and transparent, ensuring that citizens’ voices are heard, and opinions are taken into account in setting up key regional R&I policies (deliberative process).”¹

The grant agreement describes a set of interrelated objectives in that regard. The Lombardy cluster activities aim to achieve the following objectives:

¹ <https://www.transform-project.eu/lombardy/>. Accessed November 23, 2022.

“Set-up and carry-out a multi-stakeholder engagement process through participatory research agenda setting approach; Include concrete suggestions, visions and opinions from citizens and local stakeholders in the next Lombardy Region Three Years R&I Strategic Plan, aligned with regional S3; Develop a detailed operation plan which describes the whole process and can ensure the replicability of the approach in Lombardy and beyond; Hold a local final event to share learning and outcomes with local R&I and S3 stakeholders; Foster novel and transparent governance relations within the regional R&I agenda setting” (TRANSFORM Grant Agreement)

This participatory research agenda setting process consisted of a survey administered both online and via telephone to Lombardian citizens. In addition to this survey, an online workshop on just energy transition in Lombardy was organized. The idea guiding this procedure was to combine a quantitative approach - collecting data representing the Lombardy population - with a qualitative format. This qualitative format was a workshop that focused on one of the topics addressed in the quantitative survey.

In addition to this participatory agenda-setting process the Lombardy cluster also organized a citizens’ jury on data-driven smart mobility. This citizens’ jury consisted of two meetings on non-consecutive Saturdays with 24 participants in June 2022. The aim was to develop recommendations for funding calls on data-driven smart mobility that the Lombardy Region was preparing as part of its “Smart Mobility and AI” strategy from 2020.²

This overall approach resonates with much of the literature on deliberative democracy, as well as with early ambitions on the European level to give a “voice” to the citizens. This has been described as a mode of listening (Dobson, 2012). As such it counterbalances the influence of lobbies. Therefore, the additional mentioning of taking into account the citizens’ inputs. It is the concrete practice of “taking into account” that will determine the quality of the activities of this kind of deliberative formats.

The survey was designed by FGB in dialogue with Regione Lombardia and Finlombarda and was further administered by an external agency to a representative sample of people living in Lombardy (approximately 1.000 people). Furthermore, the sample was calibrated by age, gender, and province of residence.

² <https://www.openinnovation.regione.lombardia.it/en/homepage/smart-mobility-&-artificial-intelligence>. Accessed November 24, 2022.

“The first one was a survey administered to a representative sample on Lombardy population, calibrated by a series of social demographic variables. And that study was the quantitative part. Then we had the qualitative part that was at this deliberative workshop” (Int_06)

This survey was combined with a deliberative workshop entitled “Just Energy Transition in Lombardy”. To our colleagues from the Lombardy cluster the choice of this topic illustrates the importance of environmental sustainability to the Lombardian citizens. In addition, the issue of energy transition is relevant across different policy- and decision-making scales, from regional and national all the way to the supra-national level of EU policymaking. The recruiting of the citizens as well as support in facilitation was again provided by an external agency. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, this workshop was organized online. Still, our colleagues managed to bring together 18 Lombardian citizens, who were then divided into 3 different groups for break-out sessions to discuss the topic. The workshop was held as a 1-day 8-hour event on a Saturday and was structured as follows: first an informative phase with a brief introduction, an informative video, an expert presentation, and – finally - a Q&A session. Then the workshop proceeded with discussions among the participants, with some time set aside for elaboration on the recommendations. The overarching objective of these activities was to “understand the needs of the citizens”:

“In the, in our case in the participatory agenda setting it was very important to understand the needs of the citizens because the yeah, the activities were focused on these and it was very helpful and also the social demographic variables were very important to understand. Because Lombardy is a very, there is a lot of variety so you have like little villages in the mountains and a big city like Milan.” (Int_06)

Citizens are here framed as representatives of a certain region. What is described as “needs” is a placeholder for the socio-economic situatedness of the respondents to the online survey. The needs were pre-determined in the survey, but the respondents had the option to add or describe additional needs. The list of needs included the following topics: the availability of quality food in sufficient quantity, disease prevention, questions of health care in the different regions (timely and appropriate care close to home, treatment or rehabilitation at home whenever possible, innovative care and therapies), culture and art, communication & information accessibility, services for citizens (e.g. registry office, school enrollments, medical reservations), safe mobility (such as pedestrian, cyclist, motorist) & public transport, safety of living conditions, multiculturalism, the protection and inclusion

of minorities and vulnerable individuals (e.g. the disabled), violence against women, LGBTQ+-people, work safety and income.

The second step - a deliberative workshop - had to be conducted online due to Covid19-related restrictions and was framed as the “qualitative” addition to the quantitative consultation. The objective of this workshop was to collaboratively work on recommendations for work towards a just energy transition.

Building on these activities, the Lombardy cluster aimed to establish more ambitious and long-term forms of deliberative democracy. While the initial plan was to establish a citizen assembly related to Lombardian innovation policies on AI, this was later changed into the format of a citizens’ jury. In June 2022, the Lombardy cluster organized such a citizens’ jury on data-driven smart mobility. The citizens’ jury was organized as two meetings on non-consecutive Saturdays with 24 participants. Again, the participants were selected by an external agency, which also assisted in facilitating the process. The first day was devoted to providing information about smart mobility and its challenges to the citizens. This was the so-called “informative stage”. The inputs given by the experts focused on issues such as responsibility and mobility, privacy, open data, mobility, and gender. After receiving these inputs, the participants were divided into different break-out sessions where they collaboratively developed questions for the experts in a subsequent Q&A. During the second day of the citizens’ jury, recommendations were developed and then at the end of the meeting presented to representatives of the Lombardy Region. According to our colleagues from Lombardy, these recommendations are informing the design of a call for funding named “Smart Mobility Data Driven”, which itself is part of the Lombardian Smart Mobility and AI strategy from 2020.

Both pilot activities had a clear objective and purpose as well as a plan on how to impact regional policymaking. There is, however, an underlying second-order objective to these activities. The aim was not only to better understand the needs of the Lombardian citizens and subsequently to provide better – in the sense of more tailored – policies. In addition, our colleagues from Lombardy wanted to collaboratively design and conduct a methodologically sound, representative “consultation” as a showcase for the Region.

“So, the first was to really to think about representativeness of the citizens to have this broad survey with sample of representation of a population in Lombardy. So, to show the Region that that means to consult your population in a, from a strong methodological point of view (...)” (Int_05)

Such a showcase needed to be provided “from a strong methodological point of view” according to our colleagues, so that they could use the pilot activities to build capacity within the Region, and also to help convince actors who were still hesitant. In doing so, FGB could rely on the help of actors from the regional administration who were already willing to participate in this project (this is crucial in comparison to the other clusters). We will come back to this point later.

Before we unpack the activities of the Lombardy cluster, we want to describe the institutional set-up of the Lombardy cluster. The situation in this cluster is rather interesting and allows our colleagues to achieve what the other clusters could not. However, their approach also comes with its own set of challenges and risks. So, who or what is Fondazione Giannino Bassetti and what is their role within the Lombardian research and innovation ecosystem?

Fondazione Giannino Bassetti and the Lombardian R&I ecosystem

One of the central elements of the translation of RRI in Lombardy is the position of FGB within the regional R&I ecosystem and its relation to the regional administration represented by Regione Lombardia and Finlombarda. Formally, FGB is a Foundation of Participation since 2016 and the regional government is represented by its President within FGB’s Board of Participants. Also, FGB’s president Piero Bassetti was the first President of Lombardy Region from 1970 to 1974 and since its inception in 1994 the Foundation has worked together with the Region on issues of responsibility in innovation governance. This shows that there are close informal but also formal ties between FGB and Lombardy Region. The mission statement of FGB mentions a version of responsible innovation and states that it aims to “create a new and renewed awareness around the memory of a precedent, a modern and widespread sense of social, civil and political responsibility amongst those who innovate”

This means that there is a well-established history of collaboration between the different partners in this cluster. There is a clear distribution of responsibilities and roles among the various organizational actors and the overall purpose of their collaboration both in terms of the separate organizations’ interests but also when it comes to the overall aim of developing and nurturing a culture of responsible research and innovation. In this region this takes the shape of an R&I governance that increasingly relies on novel forms of

deliberative democracy, such as participatory agenda setting, citizens' juries and at some point in the future – so the plan of FGB – citizens' assemblies.

More recently, FGB played a consulting role when the Region aimed at strengthening the legal foundation for RRI within the regional governance system. The result of this ambition was that RRI now is a part of the so called “Legge Regionale 23 novembre 2016, n. 29”. This law states that to strengthen regional innovation and the competitiveness of the system a culture of responsible research and innovation needs to be established through the dissemination of and experimentation with innovative methods and processes. In addition, it also provides the legal basis for the “Forum for Research and Innovation” which has an advisory function. FGB is formally recognized as a supporting body to this forum.

This means that even before the acronym RRI became successful in the EU policy realm, FGB had already made it one of its core pillars. It therefore comes as no surprise that the relation between the different partners in the TRANSFORM Lombardy cluster is built around the idea of responsibility. One of our colleagues put it like this:

“But (laughter) if we say if we say responsible innovation, people have at least an idea okay. If we talk about the general directorate whether in some works then it is something where people more or less have a clear understanding. Okay. It's a less vague notion. So I feel/ my personal feeling is that the public regional administration, those people who know Fondazione Bassetti. These, these civil servants know that it's, probably they think that it's a leftist foundation that provides some cultural discussion okay. That people who have been in touch with Fondazione Bassetti, normally general directorate for research and innovation, know that Bassetti foundation is responsible innovation and Fondazione tries to carry on a discourse on what responsibility/ what kind of responsibility the regional administration have when they/ when it does policy innovation. Innovation policy.”

The particular set-up of the Lombardian R&I ecosystem allows for things to happen that wouldn't be possible somewhere else. However, there are also certain challenges that come with relationships like this one. In what follows, we want to unpack this translation and the network within which it co-emerges and then point to those opportunities and risks as they become visible in the work of the TRANSFORM Lombardy cluster.

Translating RRI as participatory agenda setting and citizen juries

We have thus far spent some time describing the “what” of the Lombardy cluster’s activities. We now want to delve into the “hows” and “whys” of it all. This means unpacking the activities and the ideas and concepts that are guiding them. We will start by looking at what is considered “good” engagement by our colleagues in Lombardy and how this relates to the models of engagement and subject positions that become visible in their accounts of what they are doing. Following that we will describe how the activity of “piloting” is enacted in the work of this cluster and how the distinction between a “preparatory” and “main” stage of the activities plays a role here.

“Good” engagement in the Lombardy cluster

One of the most interesting themes in the conversations with our colleagues from the Lombardy cluster was their particular idea about what constitutes legitimate purposes of RRI work in Lombardy. In that sense the rationales guiding the activities in this cluster are very clear and transparent. First and foremost, conducting pilot projects following the principles of RRI means working with policy- and decision-makers.

“And so, the responsible, all the reflections and activities of Bassetti Foundation really revolve around the concept of science and its interaction with the policy-making environment and the actors and dynamics and activity. So, you can talk about and you can make responsible innovation if you work with people really involve and key in governing innovation, which means not only of course policy-makers but the people in charge of decision-making in governance and in the government, in the governments to govern research and innovation. Of course, you can do terrific work also with innovators, with researchers but a relevant, crucial point is working with policy-makers and decision-makers.” (In_05)

As becomes visible in statements like this one, there is an emphasis on policy-making in the way our colleagues talk about RRI in Lombardy. RRI is translated as a particular form of innovation governance that is built on a top-down notion of governance. In order to change how innovation systems work, you need to start with the people who are responsible for setting the framework conditions in a given innovation ecosystem. Consequentially, policy- and decisionmakers are the primary collaborators in working towards more responsible research and innovation systems.

Not surprisingly then, the way in which the pilot activities are set up in this cluster mainly centres around innovation and its governance. Science and research, while playing a role in the work of FGB more generally, play a minor role in the Transform project.

While the cluster's participatory activities of course centre around technoscientific innovation, this translation of RRI is not mainly interested in the responsible governance of research institutions. Rather, it clearly focuses on innovation and on the production of innovation strategies. This is not surprising, as one of the main objectives of the project is to influence the development of the Regional Smart Specialization Strategies (S3) and – in the case of the Lombardy cluster – the Three Years' Strategic Plan for Research, Innovation, and Technological Transfer (PST).

This focus also clearly shapes our colleagues' understanding of what constitutes "good engagement". Good in our conversations is very often used synonymously with "real" and as such it is demarcated from "fake" participation:

"We have long history for responsible innovation. So, I don't want to have fake participatory process so just to, to say or to have a deliverable or to tweet on Twitter. Oh, we have made this wonderful workshop collecting recommendations that no one in the world will read and use somehow." (Int_05)

Statements like this and the distinctions that are drawn point to a very distinct set of challenges and risks associated with designing and conducting engagement activities. These risks that our colleagues highlight have been described in the literature on participation and engagement as "symbolic" (Dryzek et al., 2019) participation or as "tokenism" (Arnstein, 1969). Used in this way, participation becomes a mere means of window-dressing decisions that have already been made. As such, this distinction between "real" vs. "fake" points to perceived risks in the work of the Lombardy cluster. It is also a challenge that comes with working alongside administrative or government actors (Völker & Guimarães Pereira, 2021).

"Fake" here indicates engagement without any commitment to act on what has been discussed. One of the main priorities in the work of the Lombardy cluster is to make sure that the input of the citizens does actually matter in the innovation governance work. This ambition is clearly guiding how the engagement activities are set up, the choice of the partners in doing this, and also the ideas about the long-term impacts that transpire as a result of the TRANSFORM project. In short, the whole process of the Lombardy cluster is organized according to this overarching principle of having meaningful and real

engagements. While this is generally commendable, there are some risks associated with this strategy. We will return to this topic later.

Models of engagement & subject positions

These ideas about what constitutes “good” engagement is further expressed in our colleagues’ views on the actors who become involved in the deliberations, the roles they should play, and how the outcomes of these activities are supposed to enter the policy- and decision-making processes in Lombardy.

As was elaborated on in the beginning of this chapter, different versions of deliberative democracy bring together citizens with experts to deliberate on a certain topic at hand. These deliberations are supported by experts and (often) guided by professional facilitators. The outcomes of such deliberations are then fed back into the policy realm where ideally the suggestions and ideas from the citizens will have a noticeable impact on policy and decision making.

This basic model is also applied in the work of the Lombardy cluster and the main actors are virtually the same. In terms of deliberative democracy, this is a kind of “state mandated” initiative but the funding body being the EU. Therefore, the mandate is not as strong in terms of being consequential as compared e.g. to the Irish case. This version of RRI is mediated by the practice of “piloting”, which means that the activities are only partially focused on the issues at hand. Much rather the focus is to conduct a good showcase for Lombardy Region so they can be convinced about the approach and also made capable of repeating it for other issues.

The overarching objective of these activities was to “understand the needs of the citizens”:

“In the, in our case in the participatory agenda setting it was very important to understand the needs of the citizens because the yeah, the activities were focused on these and it was very helpful and also the social demographic variables were very important to understand” (Int_06)

Citizens are engaged as holders of certain “needs” that can be known through different kinds of survey and interview methods. Citizens are thus invited as experts for needs of a region and their lived experience in these regions. They are put together with experts for different technological areas such as big data and AI, open data, privacy or vehicle

construction. In addition, an expert on inclusion and gender equity was part of the citizens' jury. In some instances, these experts are also part of regional innovation clusters and have thus knowledge of and stakes in regional innovation policy.

This conceptualization also ties into a particular theory of change in which these needs of the citizenry must be expressed in order to be properly understood. Once these needs are understood by the Region, innovation strategies that are developed by the Region together with different innovation clusters (populated by "stakeholders" from industries and academia) are supposed to address these needs. The relationship between innovation policy and society in this translation of RRI is thus one of providing solutions to problems. The added value as described here is that through this engagement there can be some regional (provinces) specificity to what the Region is doing.

What is a pilot?

The engagement activities of the different TRANSFORM clusters in Lombardy, Catalonia and Brussels-Capital Region are organized as pilot projects. However, the term "pilot" means different things in the different clusters, and in some cases, they mean different things for the partners within single clusters. The ways in which pilots are understood and used differ in terms of the general purpose of piloting, the particular objectives of each pilot, and also with regard to the perceptions of risks and potentials associated with them. The conduct a pilot activity for example can take the meaning of designing an activity and "piloting" it in the sense of tinkering and experimenting with it. The goal then is to fine-tune the approach and methodology. Therefore, it is important to carve out what our colleagues talk about when they talk about pilot activities.

In the Lombardy cluster, one of the main goals of the pilot activities are to showcase the potential of participatory or deliberative approaches to governance. This is described by our colleagues as showing the partners from the regional administration something "concrete":

"So, considering the timing and the constraints to deliver the PST [the Three Years' Strategic Plan for Research, Innovation, and Technology Transfer; T.V.], we decided to go for an online survey and online workshop to have a double, to reach a double achievement. So, the first thing was to really to think about representativeness of the citizens to have this broad survey with sample of representation of a population in

Lombardy. So, to show the Region that that means to consult your population in a, from a strong methodological point of view but also to start to show what means having deliberation, what is the strength of a qualitative exercise with an online workshop.” (Int_05)

What piloting entails for our Lombardian colleagues is clarified through their emphasis on “Showing something “concrete” through piloting”. This approach does not understand piloting in the sense of experimentation or tinkering as a series of trial and errors to find the best solutions to a given problem in a certain context. Rather, piloting as it is described in the statement above clearly points to something different than slowly developing or fine-tuning a certain approach or methodology. The approach is already mature and ready to be presented. Instead, the pilot activities in Lombardy were designed to do two things: first, to showcase what can be done through engagement methods, i.e. demonstrate what the added value is. A pilot in this sense is a demonstrator. In addition, and this is crucial to note here, piloting is about showcasing diversity, showing that there are different ways to engage the public. The administrative partners from the Lombardy Region are already familiar with polling and conducting surveys. This part was primarily focused on demonstrating how this should be done in a methodologically sound way. The workshop-part of the pilot mainly focused on introducing something new and proving that this can indeed be useful and provide an added value.

A second aim the cluster partners from Lombardy kept talking about was that they wanted to give the Region something practical, something they could make use of in the future. “Practical” and “concrete” then takes on a different meaning that is more related to capacity building. It is about breaking down the approach in a way so that it can travel - travel from the experts at Fondazione Bassetti to the allies within the Lombardy Region, and to people within the region who are not yet convinced. This particular translation of RRI as concrete engagement activities and blueprints is premised on the relationship between FGB and the Region. These activities and blueprints also help to stabilize this relationship.

“We as Lombardy, I think we are strong enough under the legal framework, under the legal point of view to embed RRI in our legal system. Transform is now I think is providing (...) let’s say a concrete/ it’s something concrete that shows to [N.N.] and the rest of the group that responsible innovation is more than a principle. And okay but everybody knows. Okay so but okay but then what is it?” (Int_07)

RRI is perceived as a well-established idea or principle within innovation governance in Lombardy - thanks to the work of Fondazione Bassetti. In the accounts of our colleagues this idea is no longer challenged and doesn't need much convincing or explanation. It is even codified in the Lombardian legal system. Because RRI is so well-established, the objective of our colleague's work has changed. The activities of the Lombardy cluster hope to move beyond RRI being perceived as an abstract "principle" in the Region. In order to achieve this objective, methodological guidance and the production of some sort of blueprints is necessary. Here, then, RRI is turned into guidelines for engagement activities that rest on regional legislation.

The pilot – and the activity of piloting - conceived in this way is only possible because it can build on a decade-long history of collaboration as well as on previous work. This is visible, among other things, in institutions like the above-mentioned Legge Regionale and in the Regional Forum for Research and Innovation.

This is also visible in the particular set-up of the activities and how they are conceived in terms of the "preparatory" stage and main activities.

The "more than" preparatory stage in Lombardy

The participatory agenda-setting activities in the Lombardy are grounded in a broader idea about legitimate purposes and rationales of RRI work. As we mentioned above, first and foremost this means working with decision makers. There is a strong focus on the governance realm when our colleagues talk about RRI in Lombardy. RRI is understood mainly as a form of innovation governance where policy- and decisionmakers are the primary collaborators. In addition to this focus on RRI as collaboration with policy- and decisionmakers in innovation governance, the importance of engagement not being "fake" is crucial in the accounts of members from the Lombardy cluster. This stance clearly resonates with work pointing to the risks of "window dressing". One of the main ambitions (and priorities) in the work of the Lombardy cluster is to make sure that the input of the citizens does actually matter in the innovation governance work. The question then becomes: how can the Lombardy cluster make sure that input from citizens is used for more than mere "window dressing"?

In the accounts of our colleagues from this cluster, nurturing and maintaining a good relationship with administrative partners in Lombardy is crucial for this endeavour. A

central part of the activities in this cluster then, is what can be called “maintenance work”. Maintenance work covers activities that are devoted to building good working relationships with partners in different sectors of the research innovation ecosystem as well as efforts that go into nurturing and curating those relations. This kind of work is usually not formalized in grant agreements and descriptions of tasks and milestones. Nonetheless, as we argue, none of the activities that are covered by such texts - and are thus legitimate objects of performance and impact assessment - would be possible without well-maintained relationships and ecosystems. In the TRANSFORM Lombardy cluster maintenance involves capacity and awareness building seminars, collaboratively developing the engagement process and methods, and working towards more visibility of RRI principles on a national level.

In the conversations we had with the members of the Lombardy cluster, maintenance work becomes visible in the distinction that is often made between a “preparatory stage” and the actual “engagement activities” of the cluster. For this reason, this distinction deserves some more attention here.

In considering the core activities of the Lombardian cluster, the illustration on the project website is a good starting point.

Figure 1: Visualization of the cluster activities taken from the project website (<https://www.transform-project.eu/lombardy/>)

What we see here is the rough outline of the cluster activities of the Lombardy cluster. The main engagement activities were the participatory research agenda setting process and the citizens’ jury. As visualized in this illustration, a number of smaller activities were organized around these two core activities. Mutual learning, process design, and capacity building are here depicted as actual part of the timeline, whereas some of the other ongoing activities FGB has been doing are delegated into a separate box. So, what we see visualized here is the distinction between what our colleagues referred to as “preparatory stage” in contrast to the main cluster activities.

“So, before the concrete starting of the engagement stage, we had a preparatory stage which was the key to be sure that the public engagement activities were actually actionable from the Region. So, we had a lot of mutual learning meetings with [N.N.] and Finlombarda team. We talked about S3 and RRI and kind of mutual training let’s say and we discussed a lot about the S3 procedure.” (Int_06)

One of the key aims of the meetings in this preparatory stage was to make sure that the activities in the engagement state were “actionable”. To make them actionable is to make sure that the activities are organized on a topic that is relevant to the Lombardy Region and that some form of uptake can be granted. To achieve this, several meetings were organized to define the purpose and scope of these activities. On an underlying level, these meetings were further used to build trust and give input on RRI and various approaches to engagement and deliberation.

“We had online meetings and we also met one time here at the foundation premises but after the, the engagement process and did the, so to build the next stage. So, the first meeting in person was one month ago I would say but we knew them already and I think as we said in some other meetings it was, I think it was very important because the connection between the Foundation and the Region was already very strong. So, there was already a lot of trust. They, they know how we work and we know how they work so.” (Int_06)

Accounts like this one show another aspect of how members of the Lombardy cluster think about good engagement regarding the different stages. In order to have good engagement activities it is necessary that all partners share an understanding and a basic knowledge about what it is they want to achieve and how they want to achieve it. What is important to note here regarding maintenance work is how our colleague carefully points out that this work is premised on a pre-established relationship of trust. At the same time, however, this part of the project work also contributes to the maintenance and nurturing of this relationship. FGB – and this will become important later in comparison to other TRANSFORM clusters - could rely on an already existing network with the administrative partners within the Lombardy Region. This relationship existed before the project even started and, crucially, the people in this network were already convinced that RRI is important. This points to the importance of both mutual trust and some sort of “belief” on the side of the administrative partners:

“Yeah. And she’s really supporting the citizen engagement activities here (laughter). It’s like yeah. She really believes in this in these activities.”

These actors within the regional administration have a double role in the project and for Fondazione Bassetti beyond the TRANSFORM project. They help set up the clusters current engagement activities and make sure they are “actionable” and thus “meaningful” for the citizens. In addition to that, they try to convince colleagues within their own ecosystem

about the importance of approaches to governance that in one way or another rest on RRI principles, and in doing so hope to enrol them into the group of people who “believe” in this mode of governing. Without these actors within the administration and without the work they were doing before (and possibly after) the actual TRANSFORM project, the engagement activities of the Lombardy cluster would have very likely turned out differently than they did. Indeed, some of the activities might not have been possible to conduct at all. When we talked about this work with the regional R&I ecosystem and with their administrative partners in particular, the members of the Lombardy cluster described this relationship as dynamic. The aim is to identify actors within the administration who are interested in alternative modes of governing innovation. Once these actors are found, the next step is to build a relationship with them, so that they slowly become allies within the regional administration:

“I have seen some changes in the relationship for example especially with [N.N.], because I think I met the team from Finlombarda few times before Transform but we then saw, we already met sometime. And I think that her approach, her attitude towards this kind of engagement activities really changed a lot. Her knowledge also. And yeah. Now when we talk we are sure that we are talking about the same things and in the past years it was not.” (Int_06)

This is also where it becomes clear that what our colleagues often refer to as the “preparatory” stage is actually more than preparation, in the sense of getting the organization of engagement activities right. Of course, it is that too: it is about selecting the right topics, finding people who can assist with planning and facilitation, deciding on the concrete approaches and designs, developing a script and so on. However, there is more to this preparatory stage. What we see at play here is careful maintenance work that makes the project activities possible. Once these relationships are established, nurtured and thus stabilized to a certain degree, these actors are not only willing to support ongoing projects, but are further willing to work towards transformations within the organizational cultures of the regional administration. In a sense, they are then able to effectively “disseminate” this kind of thinking and this way of working together, within the different groups and departments of the Lombardy Region.

“We are trying to work and [N.N.] is the first person in this on pushing to try to disseminate especially within the other departments and within the Region the results and the process of Transform, because she knows quite well that she can be

moved to another department for other activities in, in any moment. So, for us at the end it's important to disseminate beyond the borders of Transform. But the real dissemination activities are within the Region and within the other departments in the three regions involved.” (Int_05)

Our colleagues, however, are keen to stress that there is a certain fragility to this kind of work. When you rely on individual allies within the administrative ecosystem there is a risk that you need to start this process over again if these actors are either moved to another group or department, or if they themselves decide to move on. Dissemination then is used in a very particular way by our Lombardian colleagues. Dissemination is not just about making people aware of project results; it is also about convincing potential future allies about the added value of engaging citizens in policy- and decision making. This is where maintenance work and the understanding and practices of piloting meet. Pilots are needed to showcase the dissemination activities, and also because the relationships with allies in the Lombardian Region need continuous maintenance and care:

“And that’s why as I said I think it’s very important that we have these outreach communication activities within the Region, within the other civil servants, with the other civil servants. We also need to plan the public, the public event to share the Transform results and also this will be very important.” (Int_06)

Parallel to the work on the project activities – which naturally is the core of the TRANSFORM cluster work and therefore also the most visible work done in the project - the cluster members are constantly reflecting on how to best nurture, stabilize and expand their network. What we see in the accounts of our Lombardian colleagues is an ongoing process of translation in the more classical sense of enrolment and enactment developed by Latour and Callon (Callon, 1986; Latour, 1987).

“it’s doing things together and talking together and trying to understand each other, the Bassetti Foundation with its own being a third party and at the same time being part of the cultural environment, shaping the public administrative discourse (laughter) I would say, okay. And now [N.N.] and the other, the other people there perceive their job okay and effectiveness of the job. And that the same/ so being a third party and at the same time working together okay and trying to make something together.” (Int_07)

The overarching objective of these activities then is framed as an attempt to have some influence on the “cultural environment” of research and innovation governance in Lombardy and as an attempt to “shape the administrative discourse”. This clearly resonates with one of the core objectives of RRI, which is to have a transformative effect on the various cultures of innovation governance (Strand et al., 2015).

While the activities outlined above very much focus on regional-level translations of RRI, part of the activities of FGB also target the national level. These activities, on the surface, are not immediately connected to the TRANSFORM-projects work. However, in the context of RRI initiatives and how these initiatives are working to create a long-term shift in innovation cultures, the overall view changes. One example of this is the recent translation of the OECD report “Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions – Catching the Deliberative Wave”:

“We decided to translate the OECD report on the deliberative wave and I think it was very interesting for us because of course we had the stronger relationship with the with the OECD but also with the region because the launch was, was very important to also to, to present our work at the national level. Because of course the translation was in Italian so it was not only for regional, Lombardy regional practitioner and for the Lombardy region ecosystem but it was for the national one. So it was a way to enlarge our audience and yeah. Our hope is to contribute to, to make the Italian context more sensitive to this kind of other approaches.” (Int_06)

This quote describes a kind of maintenance work that aims to nurture a culture of deliberative democracy beyond the boundaries of the TRANSFORM project and the Lombardy Region. The “hope” is to “make the Italian context more sensitive to this kind of other approaches” (Int_06). Translating this influential OECD report and thus making it broadly accessible to Italian innovation actors positions both the concepts and methods related to deliberative democracy - as well as FGB as an actor representing those ideas - within the Italian innovation ecosystem. This points to a practice of scaling, i.e. translating RRI from a trans- or supranational setting into the regional Lombardian and national Italian contexts. What is sometimes imagined happening more or less automatically by inserting funding into a certain system, needs constant – and in terms of project assessment often marginalized and invisible – work that involves adapting and making something fit into a certain context.

Identifying “concrete” societal challenges – actionability and relevance

We have now talked about the translation of RRI in the Lombardy cluster and addressed various elements of this particular version of RRI as deliberative democracy. In the final part of this chapter, we want to draw attention to some of the challenges that come with this particular idea of RRI as deliberative democracy. In particular the notion of “real” engagement deserves some attention, the term our colleagues from Lombardy use to describe their work with partners from the regional administration in order to make sure that the outcomes of engagement activities are relevant to the policy- and decision-making processes.

Before we further unpack this process, it is worthwhile to remind ourselves of some of the central ideas of RRI, as they clearly resonate with the idea about “real” engagement expressed by our colleagues in Lombardy.

“A transparent, interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view to the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products (in order to allow a proper embedding of scientific and technological advances in our society).” (von Schomberg, 2012)

In this quote by René von Schomberg, one of the key actors behind the idea of RRI, responsiveness is a key term. Responsiveness is one of the four dimensions of RRI (Stilgoe, Owen and Macnaghten, 2013), the other ones are anticipation, reflexivity and inclusion. The way it is presented here, it mainly refers to responsiveness between innovators and other societal actors in order to improve both innovations (as in marketable products) and the innovation process with regard to acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability. It is clearly the latter Fondazione Bassetti are interested in in their work with the Lombardy Region. Their work of co-creating pilot activities first and foremost aspire to build capacity within the regional administration in order to make their processes more responsive at improving the innovation process as such. Regional administrations responsible for innovation processes are thus imagined to become responsive to other societal actors via FGB.

Becoming more responsive indicates some form of shift or transformation both in terms of the actors involved but also with the regard to the topics to be addressed and how they are framed. This is not a one-way street of course. Becoming responsive to each other means that all actors involved will be affected as they enter into a complex dynamic process of

shifting power relations. The interesting question then becomes how the different actors are imagined to become responsive to each other and how decisions are made about the particular challenges that R&I ecosystems need to become responsive to. The story of the Lombardy cluster can be read as a story about the potential - but also the challenges - of attempts to become more responsive, as the very idea of becoming more responsive privileges some versions of RRI while marginalizing others.

When the members of the Lombardy cluster talk about their pilot activities, one of the central elements is the process in which the topics to be deliberated on are identified. In this identification process the choice of topic for the engagement, i.e. the issue to be discussed, as well as the timing of the engagement activity in regard to ongoing processes within the Region, played major roles in their considerations.

Here it is important to keep in mind that the collaboration between FGB and the Lombardy Region is already established and there is a longstanding relationship between FGB and the innovation ecosystem in Lombardy. Compared to the Brussel Capital Region cluster for example, this makes it considerably less difficult to identify fitting topics. Fitting topics are those that are able to make use of certain windows of opportunity. What this means is that topics can only become relevant for deliberation when there is an ongoing policy-process. In this way, so our colleagues argue, it is much more likely that the inputs of the citizens are earnestly considered by the administration. From the perspective of FGB and the Lombardy Region there is only added value to be demonstrated if their pilot activities are addressing topics that are currently relevant within the administrative ecosystem.

While this sound perfectly rational and pragmatic, there is a downside or challenge to this approach. Fondazione Bassetti needs to carefully navigate the line between focusing on what is relevant and important to the Lombardy Region at a certain point in time while at the same time avoiding the risk of having the process completely dominated by those same needs at the cost of the potential for bottom-up problem framings to emerge. The constellation in Lombardy makes it very easy for the administrative partners to tell FGB where RRI makes sense and where it doesn't. This practice of collaboratively defining the issues that engagement activities can and should focus on clearly resonates with the RRI idea of becoming responsive to societal challenges.

In the Lombardy cluster this notion of becoming responsive is translated into ideas about "feasibility" and "actionability". This quote shows our colleague carefully talking about what can and should be done in a certain institutional-organizational setting:

“I said that the strategy for Transform with [N.N] and Finlombarda started to say ‘Hey guys, we are here, we have to make something concrete but I know there are some constraints in terms of timing and you have to deliver something at the right time and all these kind of things’. But also, for me it’s important not to oversell what we can do and feasibility, the terms of feasibility for me are relevant and key in this process.” (Int_05)

Note how in talking about what should be done in a certain pilot the relationship between the different partners is always a key element. The pilot has to offer something “concrete” that allows them “to deliver”. Both elements are crucial for maintaining the relationship between FGB and the Region, as FGB needs to be seen as a reliable partner that does not “oversell” and is able to give the Region something they can work with. Doing something concrete is therefore closely tied to the timing of the pilot, and this is where the notion of relevance comes in. Relevance here is crucially not only a thematic but also the temporal category. Doing a pilot means doing something concrete at a certain point in time. In the fast-moving policy world reports need to be published before certain deadlines, and as a result input on particular topics is highly time-sensitive. The societal challenges RRI addresses and that the TRANSFORM RRI pilots need to be responsive to are already filtered by the regional innovation-policy process, and thus tend to have a short lifespan. The risk is that if we are not mindful of this temporal aspect the output that is produced might not be relevant, which in turn means wasting the citizens time in “fake” engagement. This framing of RRI becomes visible when our colleagues talk about the importance of honesty:

So, I preferred to do less but that’s something concrete that we can say that we are honest in this. That we have really done what we have promised. Perhaps just very little success but for me, this can be a first step of longer process but it’s something that’s honest. It’s not something that we have say oh we have done a wonderful citizen assembly and at the end we had just thirty citizens in two meetings discussing not relevant things.” (Int_05)

Honesty here means always having the long-term goal of building a culture of responsible innovation governance. To do so pilot projects must be ambitions – but not too ambitious. Our Lombardian colleagues in that sense prefer small successes instead of big events that yield no results in terms of policy impact.

This becomes even clearer when our colleagues talk about the quality of engagement. The quality is not defined merely by how closely some blueprint or guideline is followed. Rather, this is about follow up and the “usability” of the “results”:

“But again, we need to start from the policy point of view for the policy question. So, we need to have a process that can be embedded in the shaping of a policy. So, we cannot do citizen participation process for the sake of saying we are involving citizens. So, you need to use the results for something and I really would like to know what is this something for you. What is in your pipeline of the policies? So, we start from that. So, what are you preparing now in the timeframe that we have to do something concrete?” (Int_05)

This means a couple of things: first, there is a need for a result, for something presentable. Second, these results need to be timely, meaning they need to tie into a particular policy discussion that is going on at exactly the time when “the results” are ready. Finally, in terms of planning this means of course that the moment of giving input – of becoming relevant – is the starting point for planning a pilot.

Not every societal challenge can therefore be properly addressed in pilots such as the ones designed and conducted by the Lombardy cluster. A societal challenge needs to be set up in a way so that there can be concrete and actionable results to it. If this is possible there needs to be a process to identify or define the exact moment when results can be actionable and thus be “embedded in the process of shaping policies”. However, this requires considerable skill and effort, and is premised on an already existing relationship between the different partners (which needs to be constantly nurtured/maintained).

Such a relationship is the condition for being able to understand the “needs” of the regional administration and their innovation governance plans and practices. In our conversations, the cluster partners would often stress the importance of understanding what an institution plans and needs and how citizen engagement fits in there. Importantly, these “needs” are part of the translation, part of the ecosystem and part of becoming “responsive” as one of the core principles of RRI states. So, in a sense, these needs are an integral part of “the territory” or the “local” ecosystem:

“So, I think that to answer to all these challenges it was really key the preparatory work that we had at the beginning because it was crucial to have, to build this common language and also to understand the Region’s needs. Because sometimes I have the feeling that when you do citizen engagement, citizen engagement practitioners just want to do their work. But of course, you need to be helpful for the institution you’re working with. Otherwise, it’s just an exercise without a real impact.

So, it was key for us to understand their procedures, their plans, their needs, their yeah.” (Int_06)

Again, statements like this one nicely point to the importance of the preparatory work which is framed here as crucial in terms of later impact. Our interviewee makes a distinction between engagement activities that focus merely on doing the engagement work and their approach which focuses also very much on the “institution you’re working with”. A “real impact”, in this perspective, can only be achieved when you work closely with the regional administration. For this kind of work common project timeframes do not suffice since these relationships need to be built slowly and carefully. Methodology still plays a crucial role, but with a little twist. It is about showcasing how things are done and what is the added value in order to establish trust and prove the legitimacy of the engagement activities.

While this focus on actionability and “doing something concrete” is certainly a valid strategy in implementing RRI and also for working towards a long-term cultural shift within regional administrations, there is a risk to this type of strategy. The power to define and frame what counts as a relevant societal challenge remains with the administration:

“We stay in the some/ somehow the design and the implementation. We have these two. We as Transform, we have this room to be effective in designing and support implementation. Then this is according to the/ this is according to what the public administration is willing to share you know.” (Int_07)

Part of the maintenance work we learned about in the conversations with our colleagues from the Lombardy cluster has to do with carefully navigating the “room to be effective in”. Questions about what can be done at a certain point in time and where the limits and boundaries need to be constantly reflected on in order to not damage the relationship with the Lombardy Region, and to make sure that others within the administration can be convinced about this mode of working as well. This is, as one interviewee describes it, very much about “what the public administration is willing to share”.

This also concerns the roles, subject positions, and interaction repertoires that are available to the citizens participating in the engagement activities designed and set up by FGB and the Region:

“Because the technology roadmap is really, really technical and complex and sometimes I think it can be difficult to establish a real dialogue with citizens on that

kind of applications or elements or artificial intelligence. And so, at the end we will have to produce recommendations that are not so/ I had the feeling that a process on that topic would finish to produce a recommendation not very useful at the end for the policy. Not actionable. And so it's just the waste of time, public money and I prefer to have something more, more concrete, more close to daily life of citizens in which they can really produce actionable recommendation that Lombardy Region can use. So yeah. feasibility and actionability are definitely my key words for the process in, in Lombardy.” (Int_05)

In statements like this one about actionability and feasibility our colleagues – mainly representing their administrative partners and their needs – demarcate between issues, policy documents and questions that are suitable for engagement and those that are not. This points to ongoing demarcation work mainly done by the cluster partners before the citizens come into play. While perfectly understandable as a strategy to curate and nurture relationships within the regional R&I ecosystem and as a way to work towards cultural shifts within Lombardy Region, the downside is that citizens tend to become an afterthought. This resonates with longstanding concerns about citizen engagement in policymaking, namely that there are power asymmetries when it comes to the issue of who has the power to grant access and who is able to define and frame the topics that are up for debate.

This is a question of what the citizens are actually supposed to contribute to. The broad idea was to organize a citizen assembly on AI in Lombardy, more precisely the role of AI in the Region’s innovation strategy. When discussing potential contributions of the citizens to a so-called “technology roadmap” on AI this was deemed to be “really technical and complex”. The perceived danger, then, was that no “real dialogue” could be established and thus the outcome of the engagement would be “not very useful at the end for the policy”. As we described in the beginning of this chapter, the citizen assembly – while still an objective down the road – developed into a citizens’ jury on data-driven smart mobility. This shift arguably resulted in a more actionable engagement activity that could then feed into a call for funding within a smart mobility funding scheme.³

In addition, by focusing on the smart mobility topic our colleagues from the Lombardy cluster could collaborate with a new actor from the administration, which in turn meant

³ <https://www.bandiregione.lombardia.it/procedimenti/new/bandi/bandi/ricerca-innovazione/ricerca-sviluppo-innovazione/smart-mobility-data-driven-RLF12022027023>. Accessed November 30, 2022.

they were able to expand their network. The results of the citizens' jury were presented to different units within the Lombardy Region. According to our colleagues this has been crucial in order to keep the momentum going.

What we see here is that ideas about being “useful” and producing something “concrete” and “actionable” in order to cater to the “needs” of the regional administration can contribute to demarcation practices and thus influence the space for manoeuvre given to citizen participants before the engagement even starts.

This is not to say that this is necessarily a bad practice or wrong in any way. The important point to consider is that the exclusion or inclusion of citizens is mediated by the need for constant maintenance of the relationship between Fondazione Giannino Bassetti and their administrative partners. The dilemma that accounts such as the one described here illustrate, is one between aiming for actual citizen empowerment and the transfer of ownership on the one side, and the likelihood of producing something that will have an “impact” in the innovation policy world on the other.

Chapter 5 – Citizen science as innovation governance in Catalonia

Stories from the Basement

In December 2021, two of the authors of this book (Völker and Strand) rented a meeting room in a hotel downtown Barcelona. The hotel could be said to be stylish in the way that Barcelona is known for: elegant design and mindful architectural details, well-placed pieces of art within an otherwise mundane, essentially functionalist concrete building. Barcelona herself was less arty than usual, following almost two years of covid-19 with full and partial lockdowns. Restaurants and cafés were mostly open and could be visited by anyone able to show a valid corona QR pass code. Public and private offices, universities, and other enterprises, however, whose workers could work in their homes with their laptops, were still mostly closed. And the normally vibrant streets of Barcelona felt empty.

So, what kind of research fieldwork does one do when the field is closed? Our solution was to rent a room in our hotel and invite our informants there, for research interviews. Interviews that we could have performed on Teams or Zoom, but that we were glad that we did not. The way the interviews turned out, they were a reminder after the lockdowns of how profound conversations can become when they take place in a real room with real people and not between pixelated avatars and ghosts. These interviews, together with written materials, recordings, and a host of digital conversations in the years 2020-2022, form the backbone of this story about the TRANSFORM project as it developed in Catalonia; about the idea of citizen science as innovation governance; about translations of RRI at the regional level; and most profoundly perhaps, about how to think and enact a desire to transform one's own society.

In contrast to the rest of the hotel, the meeting room was anything but stylish. A windowless room in the basement with cheap furniture heaped together, it felt most of all as an interrogation cell. Under the influence of this ambience, we interviewed and questioned the key participants in the Catalan cluster of the TRANSFORM project about their activities – what they had done, what happened and how they assessed it – but the conversations roomed much more; indeed, to anticipate the conclusion of this story, the essence of all the activity was that it was more, it was more than what could be seen at first

sight. The significance of the activities was wider than their simple description. For instance, from its description one of the project pilots could seem quite mundane – an attempt to involve some citizens of the small Catalan municipality of Mollet del Vallès in an initiative for improved management of domestic waste – but it was *more than that*. It was also an activity with a transformational ambition, an attempt at changing the very culture and practice of governance in this seemingly insignificant suburbia at the outskirts of the Barcelona metropolitan area, making it a showcase for a different possible future in the whole region. To comprehend and appreciate the full value of this little suburban project and its sister pilot at Hospital Sant Pau, one needs to listen to, interpret and dwell upon the stories of the key participants. We hope that we have been able to render these stories faithfully in this chapter, though shaped by our own interpretations and analyses. However, before getting there, into the thickest stories and interpretations, we will begin with the simple descriptions: The basic idea of what the TRANSFORM project was supposed to be in Catalonia, and why.

"Citizen Science in RIS3": The Catalan Cluster of TRANSFORM

In previous chapters we have described the overall structure and content of the TRANSFORM project. TRANSFORM was conceived as a project bid. It responded to a particular call for proposals in the Horizon 2020 framework programme of the European Union, namely the SwafS-14 call that was devoted supporting the "development of territorial RRI", RRI being an acronym for the European policy concept of Responsible Research and Innovation. The TRANSFORM proposal gathered actors in three European regions – Lombardy, Brussels-Capital Region and Catalonia – all of them admittedly among the better developed regions in Europe with respect to research and innovation. The core idea of the proposal was that three regional clusters would all contribute to the strengthening of RRI (whatever that entailed) in each their region and specifically with regard to the further development of the regional S3 strategies, that is, the smart specialisation strategies. Each regional cluster would focus on a specific methodological approach. In the Catalan case, the regional S3 strategy was the so-called RIS3CAT strategy, and the chosen approach was that of citizen science. The imagined activities of the Catalan cluster were described in a specific work package, or a "WP" in project jargon, of the TRANSFORM proposal. It was called "WP4: Citizen Science in RIS3 – Catalonia Region".

The high-level objectives of WP4 included (TRANSFORM proposal WP4):

- *Embed participatory strategies and citizen science methodologies in the new RIS3CAT strategy of the Catalonia region, advancing the current efforts to incorporate RRI through the SeeRRI project*
- *Transform ongoing RIS3CAT-funded projects from the triple helix towards the quadruple helix, to incorporate bottom-up strategies, co-design customised services and boost innovation, and*
- *Set up and carry out a multi-stakeholder engagement to embed public participation and citizen science in ongoing RIS3CAT projects*

Given the call text from the SwafS-14 call of Horizon 2020, these objectives are not surprising. Indeed, something along these lines had to be offered in order to meet the expectations stated by the call. As a matter of fact, the TRANSFORM proposal received an extraordinarily positive evaluation (14.5 points, where 15 is the upper theoretical limit) and was selected for EU funding. Yet, a reflection on the level of ambition stated in these objectives compared to the size of the funded project makes it clear how daunting the task was, at least if taken literally. Catalonia is an autonomous region of Spain with close to 8 million inhabitants, with a relatively highly developed research and innovation sector and 12 recognised universities. Its smart specialisation strategy for the period 2015-2020, the so-called RIS3CAT, counted by its own with a total activity budget of 750 million euros (a considerable part of which was to be funded via the European Regional Development Fund). The Catalan cluster of TRANSFORM and the work foreseen by WP4 of the TRANSFORM proposal and later grant agreement, had a total economic value of approximately 250,000 euros and a total of 21 person-months of work, or around 7 months of work in each of the three project years. It was not even a David for transforming Goliath. It was more like a mosquito trying to transform an elephant.

Going beyond the mere numbers and looking into the content of the Catalan smart specialisation strategy, the TRANSFORM objectives did not appear less ambitious. The RIS3CAT 2015-2020 strategy was already a modern one, indeed an elephant and not a dinosaur. The original RIS3CAT strategy document repeatedly stated how the grand challenges of our time necessitate fundamental change in the direction of becoming smarter, more sustainable, and more inclusive. It emphasized the quadruple helix as a key principle. And, as alluded to by the WP4 objectives, there was already an ongoing SwafS-14 project with more or less the same objective for Catalunya, funded in the previous year, namely the so-called SeeRRI project.

Furthermore, below and surrounding the European policy jargon of smart specialisation and quadruple helices, there was the Catalan social and political context with long lines going back to the Spanish civil war (and before), through decades of oppression and resistance during the Franco regime, towards the Catalan project of building something close to a nation-state after Franco died. A landmark moment of this modern Catalan project was when the President-in-Exile of the Generalitat de Catalunya, Josep Tarradellas, returned to Barcelona and gave his first speech from the balcony of the Generalitat Palace, 23 October 1977. "Ja sóc aquí!" – Now I'm here! – Tarradellas exclaimed and thereby ended the 38-year exile of the Generalitat as the Catalan institution of self-governance, an institution with a history going back to year of 1359.

In 2017, two years before TRANSFORM, the Catalan authorities defied the Spanish state and organized a referendum on the highly contested issue of Catalan sovereignty. 40 years and 4 days after Tarradellas' speech, on the 27 October 2017, the Catalan parliament declared the independence of a new Republic of Catalonia. The declaration was annulled and severely punished by the Spanish State, with long prison sentences for its architects, for rebellion and sedition.

While we never – neither in our hotel basement nor in other TRANSFORM settings before or after – heard mention of a connection between S3, RIS3CAT or citizen science with the political quest for Catalan independence, the social and political context and sentiment was still a fact. Catalonia aspired and aspires to be a modern society with progressive policies. What counts as being progressive may vary but there is always an implicit, sometimes unspoken contrast to the recent past of Spain and the real or imagined foil of Spanish backwardness. The progressive character of the RIS3CAT can be understood in this light: In the Catalan context, research and innovation policy was possible to frame as having the ambition to be modern, progressive, participatory, transformational, and attuned to contemporary societal challenges, not only complying with EU jargon on the matter but going beyond it. What could there be left for TRANSFORM to achieve? Or perhaps the realities of the Catalan society and its research and innovation ecosystem in particular were more complex and demanding than what could be achieved by the mere discourse of its policies?

Later in the chapter, we shall return to this question about the complexity of the ecosystem. Our answer is going to be affirmative. Meanwhile, at the level of discourse, we may note how TRANSFORM carved out a role for itself by specifying one particular approach, namely that of citizen science, as its methodological foundation. TRANSFORM

Deliverable 2.4 offered a succinct description of the activities of the Catalan cluster of this project:

The aim of the Catalonia Region in TRANSFORM is to incorporate citizen science as a means of integrating RRI into Catalonia's RIS3CAT 2021-2027, its instruments and the actors of the Catalan R&I ecosystem. TRANSFORM offers an experimentation space that allows the Catalan Government to explore how citizen science could be integrated in RIS3CAT.

For this purpose, Catalonia Region is developing two citizen science pilot projects in the fields of waste and health. In addition to the pilot projects, the Catalan cluster is developing participatory webinars with the members of the Think Tank with the aim of increasing knowledge about RRI and citizen science and boost the generation of future new projects based on a collaborative framework between stakeholders.

Citizen science was less of a strategic choice than one of identity: The partner in the lead of the Catalan cluster and one of the architects behind TRANSFORM was Rosa Arias, founder and CEO of the small enterprise *Science for Change*, whose primary business model was exactly that of initiating and executing citizen science projects. With them as partners in the Catalan cluster, they had the Open Systems Research Group at the University of Barcelona, which also focused on citizen science and participatory research, as well as the Generalitat de Catalunya itself, represented by a public administrator who played a major role in developing RIS3CAT. Many organisations and individuals ended up playing a role in the Catalan cluster of TRANSFORM and its activities. The main strategic actors, however, remained the same throughout the project: Science for Change, the Open Systems Group and the Generalitat.

Why Citizen Science?

Before we continue on our journey through the Catalan cluster, it may be useful to briefly recapitulate what citizen science is and may be. The term itself is not too old. It is found in academic literature since the early 1980s but its use was very rare until the 2000s (Kullenberg & Kasperowski 2016). In 2014, it came into prominence by being included in the Oxford English Dictionary⁴. The OED definition read:

⁴ <https://povesham.wordpress.com/2014/09/10/citizen-science-in-oxford-english-dictionary/>

citizen science *n. scientific work undertaken by members of the general public, often in collaboration with or under the direction of professional scientists and scientific institutions.*

Exactly what counts as citizen science, what it is and what it is good for, are issues where opinions differ and ideas are contested. Part of the disagreement can be seen as ideological and it resembles rather closely part of the disagreements about what RRI is and should be, revolving around the questions about the legitimate role of civil society in the governance and practice of science. Should society "speak back to science", as suggested by Gibbons (1999)? Should science become more democratic?

These disagreements have attracted attention from scholars within the field of science and technology studies; indeed, their original formulation and analysis were due to STS scholars such as Alan Irwin (1995, 2001). If we follow Kullenberg & Kasperowski (2016), however, and look at research papers in which the term "citizen science" is used, the scholarly discussions about the term itself amount to a minor portion of the corpus. The majority of papers that speak of citizen science, are contributions to natural science, in particular within ecology, environmental sciences, biology and geography, and to some smaller extent fields such as computer science and astronomy. The studies engage with the term citizen science as a label to describe their research approach. Often, the approach is one of natural science with contributions from "citizens", which may be observations, use of sensors, data analysis, lending computing power from personal computers, et cetera. It is fair to say that the contributions tend to have the character of research assistance.

Moreover, as is easily observed from the OED definition, the concept of citizen science rests on some kind of demarcation between science/scientists and non-science/(lay) citizens which – for the concept to make sense – is not the philosophical demarcation between justified and less justified claims to knowledge but rather an institutional one. Citizens may contribute to science even if they are not *professional* scientists with proper scientific jobs (and salaries). "Even if" signals that their status and the terms of the collaboration with the professional scientists are not equal, though. To apply a proverbial Orwellian formula, all scientists are equal but some are more equal than others, namely the professional ones.

In parallel with and to some extent preceding the exponential growth in scientific research involving the practices of citizen science just described, there is the scholarly literature around it, arguably with STS and Alan Irwin's scholarship in the centre. In this literature, citizen science practices are critiqued, for instance for being exploitative or co-opting, but also promoted as an opportunity for a type of public engagement with science that holds a potential for citizen empowerment and the democratization of science. In this regard,

citizen science belongs to a family that includes several fields of practice. An older and possible more prominent family member is the tradition(s) of participatory action research that have roots back to Kurt Lewin in the 1940s and that proliferated in several continents in the 1970s also as part of civil rights movements. Other neighbouring concepts are those of community-based research, public participation, science cafés, participatory technology assessments, social/participatory innovation, living labs and so on. The growth of the institutional practices of research ethics are perhaps also to be seen as relating to the same family. Indeed, one way of looking at the invention and incorporation of the concept of Responsible Research Innovation is to see it as an attempt to gather many of these quite diverse strands of ideas and practices into an over-arching concept that could coordinate efforts, communities and policies that all ultimately seeked a better alignment between scientific practices and institutions with civil society and its ethical and political values. In the European Commission definition of RRI, citizen science would then naturally fit within the so-called policy key of public engagement, and also with the later policies on Open Science.

A central issue at stake, then, for citizen science and RRI and not the least their intersection, is the degree to which the activities or practices concerned actually hold an emancipatory or empowering potential for society to speak back to science and for citizens to shape the scientific practices and projects or technological innovation processes to which they contribute. In the absence of such a potential, citizen science may become just another instance of what Arnstein (1969) criticized as tokenism or de facto non-participation, simply serving purposes of informing, placating, manipulating and co-opting the public. This risk is present for citizen science but also for any other contemporary practice within the family of public participation and/or engagement with science and technology (Völker & Guimarães Pereira, 2021).

Returning to the Catalan cluster of TRANSFORM, two of the main actors – Science for Change and the Open Systems Group – were practitioners and indeed experts within the field of citizen science. Both of them were associated with the Barcelona Citizen Science Office, which was created by the city council of Barcelona in 2012. This office as well as our two protagonists all recognise the diversity of citizen projects. In the website of the Citizen Science Office, four levels of citizen science are described: (1) crowdsourcing, (2) distributed intelligence, (3) participatory research and (4) collaborative research⁵. The higher the level,

⁵ <https://www.barcelona.cat/barcelonaciencia/ca/ciencia-la-ciutat/la-ciencia-i-la-ciudadania/ciencia-ciudadana/oficina-de-ciencia-ciudadana>. Accessed December 20, 2022.

the more deeply engaged are the citizen participants and the higher their responsibility. The website, our informants and indeed the scholarly literature on the field agreed, however, that the maximum level is not necessarily always optimal. It depends on the nature and purpose of the project. Still, the emancipatory and empowering purpose of citizen science was key to the actors in the Catalan cluster, and this idea was very vocal within the Open Research Group:

"... they just want people engaged there and just answering questions and get the aggregated data and that's it. That's not what we wanted at all. And that's one of the tensions that is fully present in citizen science, I would say." (Interview)

In terms of the levels just mentioned, their ambition was that of participatory research where citizens are invited as epistemic actors who possibly may be the real experts on some part of reality that the professional scientists did not even know about. However, the ambition went beyond that of improving science by enriching it with more epistemic actors. It went beyond the demarcation of science and society as such and, as the name indicated, viewing society as open systems:

"... OK, so we can do a very nice project with a lot of data and so on but what is next? What is going to happen with that?" (Interview)

What is going to happen in the community? How can good, progressive processes be initiated and catalysed by for instance citizen science, as a means for public experimentation that arises out of concrete issues? In the words of the Citizen Science Office of Barcelona, how can citizen science be a vehicle for "improving reality"?

The vision of improving reality via citizen science and RRI was also vocal in Science for Change:

"... you are actually trying to solve real challenges with people, involving people who are, in the case of citizen science, actively contributing to the research, the results [...] and the final product of that would align with society for sure because you are working with society but also it will be much more innovative." (Interview)

It will be more innovative because the diversity of actors involved will (hopefully) lead to a diversity of ideas and approaches. Such a vision of citizen science implicitly places it on the higher ambition levels for participation and collaboration, whether placed on Arnstein's famous ladder of participation or within the more mundane four-level taxonomy used by the Barcelona office. While practices may vary, the flavour of citizen science as it was conceived in Catalonia shows its ideological connection to Irwin and the critique of the deficit model and back to the traditions of participatory action research.

RRI can be seen to have come conveniently into this matter. The status of RRI as a cross-cutting principle of Horizon 2020 provided funding opportunities as well as EU-level political justification of whatever could be recognised as RRI. In Science for Change, RRI and citizen science were considered as mutually conducive of each other. In their conception, citizen science is a practical approach that can be used to implement the normative values of RRI principle. Conversely, the normative force of RRI gives directionality to citizen science so that it indeed aligns well with society and takes the desired emancipatory and innovative character. In fact, in Science for Change, even the so-called RRI policy keys of the European Commission (gender equality, ethics, public engagement, science education, open access/open science and possibly governance) were considered to have instrumental value in that they could be applied to citizen science projects as questions or challenges. One may address the gender dimension of the project, the ethical challenges, and so on.

In short, several longer threads can be identified in the textile of the Catalan cluster of TRANSFORM and its notion of citizen science: The legacy of participatory action research that in a way was reinvented in parts of citizen science; the many different forms of public engagement with science and technology that were assembled into the umbrella concept of RRI; and the social and political project of creating a modern and progressive Catalonia by "improving reality".

RIS3CAT: Third generation innovation policy at the regional level

Still, the mandate of TRANSFORM was not simply to perform or promote citizen science. The stated purpose of TRANSFORM was to integrate the principle of RRI into RIS3CAT, the smart specialisation strategy of Catalonia, *by use* of citizen science. It should, to once again quote TRANSFORM Deliverable 2.4, offer "an experimentation space that allows the Catalan Government to explore how citizen science could be integrated in RIS3CAT".

In this way, citizen science became the translation of RRI in a double sense. The desired end result, which was to integrate RRI into RIS3CAT, was translated as the integration of citizen science into RIS3CAT. And the means by which to do so, that is, the RRI intervention of TRANSFORM, was also conceived as citizen science. The explanation or rather, the theory of change by which this would be possible, was one of exemplary learning. TRANSFORM would do citizen science and thereby show the Generalitat that citizen science could be well integrated into RIS3CAT. There are several subtleties to be commented in this double translation, and they will be illustrated by the empirical detail below. However, we may

already now observe that the implicit theory of change presupposed that the citizen science achievements of TRANSFORM indeed would become exemplary. It is hard to see how they could serve the transformational purpose if they happened to fail or be seen as weak or unpurposeful.

Another subtlety is the issue of how an experience or achievement becomes perceived as exemplary. What kind of work is needed for something to shine and to be seen as a good example, both by those shining and those seeing?

And finally, one could ask about the validity of the translation of RRI into citizen science. There were at least two answers to this question, answers that were not mutually exclusive. First, within the described "progressive" context, the ideal of citizen science was connected to public engagement and the idea of empowering citizens to speak back to science and shaping research and innovation. Secondly, in the Science for Change vision already mentioned, the citizen science to be applied was infused with the values embodied by the RRI policy keys of the European Commission. TRANSFORM should do "RRI-laden" citizen science.

From within what actors in Horizon 2020-funded RRI projects sometimes called "the RRI bubble", that is, the loosely organized epistemic network of researchers, consultants and what in technical EU jargon would be called "beneficiaries" of such project grants, the assumptions made in this story of integrating RRI in RIS3 strategies by use of citizen science might be seen as making perfect sense. In general, outside of the RRI bubble, the argument is not self-evident at all. Within the sphere of smart specialisation strategies, there is a diversity of ideas and practices. While some of them would be compatible with the idea of citizen science for transformation, for others that idea would be rather alien.

In Chapter 3, we presented the stated rationale of smart specialisation and RIS3. It may be recalled that the RIS3 requirement, that is, that regions should develop their own smart specialisation strategies, was introduced as a part of EU's cohesion policy. The explicit objective was economic transformation to boost economic growth and job creation by focusing – specialising – on regional strengths in industry and R&D that could result in competitive advantage. From the Brussels perspective, this was a way to ensure good use of EU subsidies. Regions could continue to receive money from the EU via the ESIF – the European Structural and Investment Fund, of which the European Regional Development Fund is a part – but only if they presented objectives on and a strategy for building

competitive advantage in the form of an RIS3 plan. How to do that, was explained in the policies but also in more practical documents such as the RIS3 Guide.

Otto von Bismarck famously compared law-making to the making of sausages. Both types of processes tend to produce composite results. Smart specialisation can be seen as its own bubble with its own complex and heterogenous epistemic network, and RIS3 policy documents are highly composite. On one hand, the macroeconomic perspective is strong; it is a growth policy. On the other hand, the growth is supposed to be not only smart but also sustainable and inclusive. The RIS3 guide also contains advice on social innovation, on the need for stakeholder participation, and on innovation within a quadruple helix mindset. Taken as text, the RIS3 guides and factsheets cannot help leaving the impression of cognitive dissonance, witnessed in, for instance, the use of words such as "citizen". In the official RIS3 factsheet, citizens are never mentioned. In the 2012 RIS3 Guide, the word is indeed used a dozen times. Sometimes, the citizens are envisioned as active participants; at other times, they are imagined as users of innovations and consumers of products; and occasionally they are simply objects to be observed and governed, as in the following description of research infrastructures: "Their know-how helps European industry develop new pharmaceuticals and high-performance materials, monitor the earth's oceans and air, and track the changing social attitudes and behaviour of our fellow-citizens." (RIS3 Guide, p. 74) And if we look at the endorsed methodology to monitor how the regions are performing, the so-called Regional Innovation Scoreboard, there is nothing there that has a taste of RRI, citizen science or the need for civil society to speak back to science. The indicators all belong to a combined technocratic and macro-economic paradigm, measuring investments, numbers of patents and publications, percentage of population with higher education or digital skills, and so on.

The advantage of the dissonance and ambiguity in the documents, from a practical political perspective, is that quite diverse regional approaches can be justified and find endorsement. It was fully possible to write an RIS3 plan that is little more than a business-as-usual second generation innovation policy strategy that addresses systemic features of the regional innovation ecosystem, perhaps with some attention given to sustainability challenges. However, it was also possible to find justification for more radical approaches, not the least also with the growing attention to transdisciplinarity and wider concepts of transformation in OECD policy. In scholarly literature on regional development policies, the idea of seeing as S3 as an opportunity for wider transformations has gained some traction (Fitjar et al. 2019, Coenen nd).

The RIS3CAT was exactly such an example of a more radical approach, aligning itself not only with the concepts of quadruple helix and social innovation but also the diagnostic and rationale of third generation innovation policies. In addition to the more conventional (and mandatory) S3 instruments, RIS3CAT contained a set of foci for development of public policy which included digital agendas, entrepreneurship and education but also eco-innovation and "non-technological innovation". Social innovation was highlighted in the latter as processes to address neglected social needs and to develop new social relations and new forms of collaborations in society: "The processes involved in social innovation result in learning, commitments and transformations that take place at the local level and that have to be based in the participation of local actors, empowerment and civic commitment." (RIS3CAT, p. 52, our translation)

In sum, one can observe that the objectives of the TRANSFORM project and the orientation of RIS3CAT were both compatible and incompatible. They were compatible because RIS3CAT already was situated within third generation innovation policy and within the mindset of participation, empowerment and transformation. In this sense, citizen science was a plausible addition. At the same time, the expressed objective of TRANSFORM – to transform RIS3CAT by integrating citizen science (as a form of or proxy for RRI) – was perhaps more relevant for satisfying the SwafS call under which TRANSFORM was funded than for RIS3CAT itself. The underlying normative rationale of RRI could be seen as present already in RIS3CAT. Indeed, the very idea of a small EU-funded action as a change agent for a public policy, even if it were possible, raises principled, democratic issues, at least if the change is construed in terms of conventional intervention logic, asking for the project to have "impact" on public policies. In the Catalan cluster of TRANSFORM, however, the problems of intervention logic was not really an issue because all partners operated within mindsets of network governance – two partners specialising in the more empowering end of citizen science and the regional authority partner (the Generalitat) acting in a third generation framework. As summarized by one of the Generalitat representatives: "Projects don't change policies." Projects such as TRANSFORM take place within a complex ecosystem of actors and contribute to the governance takes place within this complexity. They do not govern the complexity by themselves. Projects neither can nor should change policies; and the success of such projects depends on understanding this in practice while somehow satisfying expectations of the European Commission who ask for "policy impact" of the project. This is yet another instance of translation, from the imaginary of intervention logic to the reality of network governance (and sometimes back to the imaginary, by the use of indicators and other reporting devices).

The Pilots: Citizen science in waste management and health management

From the analytical perspective of network governance, a lot may be going on in and around a project, such as informal negotiations and deliberations, learning processes and many other things. We shall return to this. From a more formal project perspective, however, the Catalan cluster of TRANSFORM undertook two types of activities as foreseen by the project proposal and the grant agreement, namely the "think tank" and the local pilots. The project established a Catalan RRI think tank with a variety of members recruited from the regional innovation ecosystem, and it ran meetings with the think tank throughout the project period. Furthermore, the Catalan cluster designed and undertook two pilot projects within the greater TRANSFORM project that sought to explore and demonstrate the value of citizen science methodologies. One such pilot was already foreseen in the proposal phase of TRANSFORM, namely an initiative that introduced citizen science elements in an ongoing policy process on waste management in a small Catalan municipality called Mollet del Vallès. The other pilot was defined during the project period and originated from deliberations in the think tank. Its topic was treatment of endometriosis at the Hospital Sant Pau in Barcelona, and it set up a participatory co-creation process with patients and medical staff at the hospital.

Waste Collection in Mollet del Vallès

One of the Catalan TRANSFORM pilots applied a citizen science approach to work with young citizens (secondary school pupils) in the suburban town Mollet del Vallès and several departments of the municipality with the aim to improve local waste collection practices. Together with the youngsters, the local authorities and students from a Catalan university, the project group co-designed a serious game, an interactive digital waste game called Dilemma-R. Subsequently, the waste game was used by the secondary school students to elicit preferences for waste collection practices among citizens in the town. The exercise was deemed successful also in the very practical sense that it yielded results that were incorporated into the next public tender for waste collection in Mollet del Vallès.

For a glossy leaflet about the TRANSFORM project, we could stop the story about the waste game pilot here. It was perceived as a success; it achieved its concrete objectives and it provided the Generalitat with a proof-of-principle that citizen science methodologies can

deliver the expected results. In that sense it contributed to the overall purpose of exemplary learning towards the integration of citizen science in the next RIS3 strategy of Catalonia.

Furthermore, in the language of RRI, the pilot could be described as aligning the local technical waste collection system better with the values, needs and demands of the local population. The role of the young participants was above all to serve as ambassadors and door openers to the wider population of the town. In terms of the RRI AREA framework, the game created a space for reflection, engagement, and deliberation, to which the municipality proved itself as responsive by virtue of policy uptake of the results of the deliberative exercise. In terms of the notorious "policy keys" of the European Commission, there was public engagement and perhaps also some science education.

And yet, someone unfamiliar with the project and its context might wonder what suburban waste collection has to do with regional innovation or responsible research and innovation for that matter. Was the waste game an innovation, and if so, a notable one? Was this technoscience? Was there even research? The exercise looked quite different from the type of RRI initiative and practices that we will present as a contrast in Chapter 8, in consortia and endeavours that have their core in academic research environments within biotechnology. Also, bearing for instance the indicators of the Regional Innovation Scoreboard in mind, it could be hard to see how the waste game pilot had anything to do with the sort of thing that the scoreboard aims at measuring. For instance, there was no apparent business model for the waste game and seemingly no job creation involved (other than the work created by the TRANSFORM grant agreement itself). One could easily imagine innovation economists and policymakers discard the glossy leaflet and dismiss the story about Mollet as neither relevant nor noteworthy.

To appreciate the real significance of the waste game pilot, one needs to return the regional context, the transformative ambitions of RIS3CAT and the work modes of the Generalitat in their implementation of RIS3CAT.

We will begin by setting the scene in Mollet del Vallès. Mollet is a town with 51,000 inhabitants (2021) located less than 20 kilometres East of Barcelona, in the county of Eastern Vallès. Its history goes back to the 10th century. However, the character of the town has changed with the growth of Barcelona and its metropolitan area. Mollet is not part of the formally defined Metropolitan Area of Barcelona but belongs to the so-called second "corona" or (half-)crown around it. Still, to travel by train from Barcelona to Mollet is a

continuous experience of urban and suburban spaces and infrastructures. As many of the other municipalities surrounding the big city, its challenges are shaped by these infrastructures, with the AP-7 highway at its North border, railways criss-crossing the space, an enormous car park for unsold cars next to the town, and a population that doubled between 1960 and 1970, and then again between 1970 and 1990. The latter years, however, the population size has been more or less stable. One way of understanding this, is that the place is quite full, that is, unless its agricultural and industrial areas to the North and East are urbanised.

For the TRANSFORM purpose, there were several features of Mollet that could be seen as attractive. First and most important of all, the local authorities were interested in participating in the pilot. This might have been a contingency. On the other hand, this could also be due to a more general motivation related to the social and geographical context itself. Mollet is one example of these towns around Barcelona that now find themselves within a huge urban landscape and with relatively newly shaped populations and that share both the desire and need to further develop their identity as communities and "improve reality", to paraphrase the Barcelona Citizen Science Office. Perhaps less than a top-down strategic consideration, the choice of going to Mollet emerged out of the interactions of the Catalan RRI think tank, to be described below.

Mollet turned out to be a happy choice. In the city of Barcelona itself, perhaps, there would be a longer history for citizen science and for public participation exercises, but on the other hand Barcelona in its entirety would be too big for a small project such as TRANSFORM to manage. In Mollet, the project partners could get to interact with the relevant actors within the technical and financial services of the municipality. Moreover, they were able to cover the town by reaching out to its secondary schools. Indeed, it was highlighted by one of the partners that participation mechanisms that go through the school system make for geographical coverage, simply because there are schools where people live. By making the youngsters the "ambassadors" of the project, gates were opened to the entire community through their parents and other relatives and neighbours.

At the same time, it could even be argued that the short history of Mollet as a society and community in its present form, with a large influx of population little more than one generations ago, indeed would provide a stronger proof of concept of citizen science methodologies than in a community with an older civic texture.

The topic of waste was already highlighted in the TRANSFORM project proposal as a well-suited one, before the decision about the location of the pilot. Still, for citizen science to make sense in the TRANSFORM context, it would have to fulfil the objective of engaging with actual problems perceived by the citizens. As one interviewee told us, “it would be nice if we can work with somebody’s real challenges” (Int_01). This in turn also means, that the particular situation – the regional context – in which this pilot takes place strongly shaped what was being done:

So, what we want to do with the game is to co-create with people like the ideal waste collection system for their neighbourhood. And then you of course need to be able to implement that. So also people in charge needs to be flexible and understand that maybe not all one solution fits all. That maybe you need to have different solutions for the different neighbourhoods. (Interview).

In the sense that engagement was achieved by means of the waste game, it may be concluded that the issue of waste collection found interest in this community. Indeed, in the streets of Mollet, one can observe signs of the local authorities giving attention to waste separation, see figure 2:

Figure 2: Photos from Mollet del Vallès, Roger Strand, 2022.

We were surprised to see mini-recycling stations such as the one depicted, with separate entries for cork, inkjet cartridges, LED lamps, batteries, small electronics, and others. The outcome of the pilot was not "smart" in the sense of making these solutions more digital or more dependent on solutions delivered by technoscience. Rather, what the pilot tried and what it did, was to improve transversal communication and collaboration in the municipality of Mollet del Vallès. Young and old citizens got to communicate with the municipality in new ways on a public issue of interest. And perhaps equally important, the pilot developed transversal communication between the technical, financial, and educational services. This may sound as a commonplace but was not perceived as such in the local context, and it required a long-term process of developing mutual understanding and a shared language.

In terms of RRI, we can see this as a translation of RRI that aims for responsiveness at the community level of knowledge production. In terms of RIS3CAT, it was a proof of principle that a citizen science approach could be conducive of non-technical, social innovation aimed at developing and deepening social relations within the community, on an issue of public interest, for the common good, but not without potential controversy. This may not be so important if the goal is short-term boosting of the Regional Innovation Scoreboard. It is more important if the goal is to address transformation failures in regional development, in light of third generation innovation policy.

Endometriosis in the First Person

Based on the interactions and ideas that emerged in the Catalan think tank (see also below), an additional pilot was defined with the objective of improving services for the diagnosis, care and support for women suffering from endometriosis. Endometriosis is a disease connected to the female reproductive system. It is associated with immense pain and, while being a serious condition, it is often diagnosed only several years after onset of the symptoms.

The pilot was called "Endometriosis in the First Person" and employed a citizen science approach with patients and medical staff at Hospital Sant Pau in Barcelona. The Catalan Agency for Health Quality and Assessment was also part of the initiative. The goals of the pilot activity were twofold: Co-creation of recommendations to inform a new protocol for endometriosis care in Catalonia, and capacity-building and improved transversal

communication and collaboration between public administration, health personnel and patients.

As with the waste pilot in Mollet, the participants of the endometriosis pilot deemed it a success. Recommendations were indeed agreed upon and presented in a policy brief (Salas Seoane, 2022). The brief presented key dimensions of the qualitative findings from the participatory research conducted. They contained rich accounts of how it is to live with endometriosis, in terms of psychological, social and physiological experiences and their strategies to cope with the illness. Among the key dimensions were the experience of gender stereotypes and negligence in medical care when trying to get help. The recommendations focused on awareness raising, early diagnosis, and improvements in health care by better involvement of the patient in the clinical decision-making. As far as we could observe, all actors expressed enthusiasm about the pilot's ability to energise the communication between and among the patients and the health care personnel:

“[I]n her team there were some other people working on that and she saw a very good opportunity to advance in a different way on this. To talk with the patients and involve them in all of the process. And they are super happy and in fact they are changing the protocols in the hospital.” (Interview)

Figure 3. Facsimile from the endometriosis policy brief, Salas Seoane (2022), p. 5-

The activity thus combined a conventional research interest with a willingness to do things differently by involving the patients. What we see here is the application of citizen science to gather information on the needs of a vulnerable group of people and then involve members of this group in the creation of an improved health service protocol. At the time of writing (2022), there were prospects of funding and thereby continuing the process further also after the end of TRANSFORM as an EU-funded project. Just as with the waste pilot, it could be concluded that the endometriosis pilot both reached its local objectives and presented a showcase for how citizen science methodologies could be applied, in this

case in a research process coupled to public innovation in the health care sector. RRI dimensions of reflexivity, inclusion and responsiveness could be invoked in the description, as well as policy keys of public engagement and not the least gender equity.

And yet, for potential actors in the S3 bubble who are unfamiliar or uninterested in the value-based discourse of RRI, the pilot could appear as rather remote or uncoupled from smart specialisation as a growth strategy. Additionally, one could imagine critical voices from within nursing science and other fields of health care research who might argue that what was presented of results and recommendations, is all well-known from the international research literature on endometriosis, and that one does not necessarily need citizen science to do qualitative health research.

The latter point may not be so relevant at the local level, however. One informant from the hospital described to us that the TRANSFORM pilot actually made a significant contribution simply by creating an arena for dialogue between patients and doctors. Indeed, the informant described a context in which there was little communication even among gynaecologists treating the same patient, especially if they worked at different hospitals. To involve patients in knowledge production signified a huge step in such an environment. Again, we see how a TRANSFORM pilot initiates transversal dialogue, if not across an R&I ecosystem, then in a local environment that perhaps ought to have had more dialogue before but as a matter of fact did not.

From the RIS3CAT perspective, the pilot could be seen to demonstrate concrete steps towards results that promised an "improved reality", in this case for women with a painful and much neglected condition. Even more, it showed that concrete initiatives could emerge out of a construction such as the Catalan think tank. It provided a proof-of-principle of something like the think tank being able to be a generator for concrete change, that is, it demonstrated the value of a structure and not just a method. Let us therefore move from the pilots to the think tank itself.

The Catalan Think Tank

A main element of the TRANSFORM project in Catalonia was the establishment of a Catalan RRI think tank with more than 50 representatives from regional and local policy-making organisations, companies and academic organisations belonging to the Catalan R&I ecosystem. It was formed during covid-19 lockdown and had to base itself on online

platforms from which it conducted a quite extensive set of meetings and webinars, organised by Science for Change. Originally, the think tank was envisioned with fewer participants. Due to high interest, however, it was decided to increase its size.

The initial focus of the think tank was to build capacity and interest in RRI among the participants. Next, it proceeded gradually to map and develop common interests for RRI activities. Various possibilities for joint initiatives were explored, and the most concrete outcome was the endometriosis pilot at Hospital Sant Pau. Furthermore, although the waste pilot was anticipated already in the TRANSFORM project proposal, the localisation into Mollet del Vallès happened through the interactions in the think tank.

As it happened, the think tank came to serve several purposes. At a straightforward level, it likely led to increased awareness and knowledge of RRI and participatory methodologies among its members. We believe so also because it was corroborated by documentation from the webinars and meetings. Less certain but not unlikely, it may have had a further impact on the level of RRI awareness and knowledge in the wider ecosystem – that is, if the think tank participants informed their colleagues and other actors about their experiences. Next, the endometriosis pilot was – as mentioned – a proof in principle that the think tank could serve as a generator of such initiatives. This was particularly interesting for Science for Change, whose business model and *raison d'être* indeed is to perform citizen science projects. Importantly, though, the Think Tank was also an initiative to connect representatives of institutional actors across the R&I ecosystem with an actual or potential interest in RRI or more generally the transformative agenda of RIS3CAT. From the point of view of the Generalitat, or more specifically its General Directorate of Economic Promotion and Regulation, the think tank was an experiment to improve connectivity and new patterns of collaboration within the quadruple helix, and it served to extend the relevant ecological network and fortify its transformative character. To do so, it was important to emphasize the think tank as an arena for actors with that interest, an emphasis that was more general and extended beyond the think tank:

"People who want to transform, I help them. If they don't want to transform, they don't care and I don't care. [...] I tell everybody if you want to transform, you are in the right room. If you want money to do the same, next door please." (Interview)

From this perspective, it was also natural to expect that some actors disappeared as the work in the think tank developed. Not everybody could be expected to have a real interest in RRI or transformative change, or even if they were interested, to see how to engage with RRI in their own work. The aim was not to keep the think tank as big as possible but to

crystallize and stay with a network of dedicated individuals who shared the overall ambition.

In terms of the TRANSFORM proposal and grant agreement, the think tank was at the same time both less and more ambitious than the original objectives. It did not "transform ongoing RIS3CAT-funded projects from the triple helix towards the quadruple helix" or "embed public participation and citizen science in ongoing RIS3CAT projects". People were not invited nor took part in the think tank as objects to be transformed. Such grant agreement objectives that are formulated in an intervention logic, remain quite disconnected from the actual context. Instead, it created and nurtured a new network of actors inside the R&I ecosystem who got to know something about RRI in the smart specialisation context, who got to know each other and not the least know that who else shared their interests and value orientations. It was set up to stimulate agency.

From the point of view of the Generalitat, then, the continued existence of the think tank after TRANSFORM was less of a priority. It had served its purpose. We may contrast this point of view with the interests of a service provider such as Science for Change, for which the think tank could be an instrument to continue to tap into the needs and interests of the local network.

Doing RRI as citizen science and “more than that” in Catalonia

What did the Catalan cluster of TRANSFORM achieve? Did the project fulfil its objectives? We may recall the TRANSFORM WP4 high-level objectives:

- *Embed participatory strategies and citizen science methodologies in the new RIS3CAT strategy of the Catalonia region, advancing the current efforts to incorporate RRI through the SeeRRI project*
- *Transform ongoing RIS3CAT-funded projects from the triple helix towards the quadruple helix, to incorporate bottom-up strategies, co-design customised services and boost innovation, and*
- *Set up and carry out a multi-stakeholder engagement to embed public participation and citizen science in ongoing RIS3CAT projects*

Above we presented the pilots and the think tank, which in a strict sense cannot be said to have "transformed ongoing RIS3CAT-funded projects" but in other, alternative ways to introduce RRI and citizen science into Catalan society. As for the first and boldest objective, in November 2022, one month before the end of the TRANSFORM project, the Catalan Generalitat approved their new RIS3CAT strategy, the so-called RIS3CAT2030 (Figure 4):

Figure 4. Table from the new regional smart specialisation strategy of Catalonia, GenCat (2022), p. 12.

The table summarises the envisioned workings of the new strategy: "RIS3CAT will promote transformative and responsible research and innovation with impact on the quality of life of the persons in the territory." It will do so by drawing on generic technologies and new digital and technological industries but also by shared agenda-setting – all of this quite similar to the previous strategy. The high-level reference to RRI is new, however, and the shared agendas include "a system of education and knowledge production which is reflexive, anticipatory, inclusive and responsive" – a direct reference to the AREA framework of responsible innovation. Further down in the text, citizen science is explicitly mentioned as an instrument of change:

"More concretely, the development of citizen science will be promoted, of science at the service of the persons and science done together with the persons. To do so, the social and cultural actors will be involved in the identification of the challenges of the territory and the proposal and design of research and innovation projects that may provide solutions to the problems that concern the persons." (RIS3CAT2030, p. 14)

Viewed at a distance, then, the mission was accomplished: RRI and citizen science came indeed to be included in the regional smart specialisation strategy.

And yet, just as with the individual pilots, there is more to say. When we view the case more closely, the success seen at a distance becomes blurred if not superficial, while other, subtler achievements come into focus. To begin with the question of the "mission accomplished", one could argue that even if the verbiage of RRI, the AREA framework and citizen science was not prominent in the previous RIS3CAT strategy, the underlying ideas were already present, as described earlier in this chapter. The specific mention of the methodology of citizen science could still be important, though, not the least for the Catalan actors who are specialists within citizen science.

More to the point, perhaps, one could ask if the inclusion of RRI and citizen science rightly could be attributed to TRANSFORM, or at least the activities of TRANSFORM. Was it the case that TRANSFORM "impacted" the Catalan Generalitat so that it came to change its smart specialisation strategy? To stay with the impact metaphor, were the TRANSFORM activities a kind of projectile that hit the Generalitat with sufficient momentum to shift its course?

Without depreciating the achievements of TRANSFORM, we believe the projectile and momentum metaphor makes no justice at all to what actually happened. The project was not a case of a set of RRI specialists/activists who acted upon the regional authorities to achieve a sort of behavioural change in them. Indeed, similar to the collaboration in Lombardy (see Chapter 4), also in Catalonia we see a strong connection between the RRI researchers/consultants/experts partners (Science for Change and the Open Systems Group) and the administrative partner (the Generalitat and specifically its General Directorate of Economic Promotion and Regulation). The Generalitat played a very active role in defining the content of the project.

It is in this light that one can fully appreciate the quote we introduced earlier, said by the main administrative partner: "Projects don't change policies." Equipped with Occam's Razor and the timeline of TRANSFORM and the two RIS3CAT strategies it may look like TRANSFORM was the efficient cause of the inclusion of RRI and citizen science into RIS3CAT2030. From the perspective of the Generalitat, however, TRANSFORM was a means by which an already desired strengthening of the regional strategy with the conceptual planes of RRI and citizen science could take place. It was rather a case of policy changing (or defining) the project than the other way around. Or better, it was a case of network governance where a diversity

of actors were able to pursue common goals in the presence of slightly different long-term objectives.

There are interesting translations taking place in this instance of network governance. We have seen how the pilot activities were exemplars of a multi-faceted translation of RRI as citizen science. First, there is an element of gathering the needs and expectations of citizens in order to integrate them into policy- and decision-making processes. This idea is supplemented with the aim to work on “real challenges” (interview) in the region through “involving people that are (...) actually contributing to the research” (interview). Hence, actors on different levels are ascribed agency in these pilots, they are conceptualized as epistemic actors. Still, there was also an element of education and awareness raising in the translations of citizen science in the Catalan activities, something that is quite common in citizen science projects, see e.g. Strasser et al. (2019).

The insistence on real challenges and actual contributions is highly interesting in our view. The pilots imagined in the planning phase were left because the work in the think tank pointed towards something "real":

“I mean we talk first with the more active actors in the think tank and it was the city council of Mollet del Vallès on waste and they agreed to lead the challenge to, to define the pilot on that area. Then with Hospital de Sant Pau where we are working with endometriosis, and they just agreed. (...). So, we couldn't have the three but these two we're running and they're working very well because they are real.”
(interview)

Here we see how the idea to have “real” activities is closely linked to the model of citizen science as co-creation and a form of participatory governance that is a central pillar of this cluster. The think tank was the central means for integrating local administrative actors and other regional actors. What is important to note here, however, is that this kind of integration and creation of responsiveness may reach well beyond the project-lifetime of TRANSFORM.

“And in fact, the idea at the beginning was to have much less people in the think tank. I think in the proposal you only need to have like ten people involved but because in this case, [NN] is the right key player and involved a lot of people. And then that's why we had so many people at the first session especially of the think tank and then the pilots were so successful.” (interview)

There are two things that are noteworthy here. First, this is about temporalities and the limits of R&I governance through project funding. One of the reasons why the think tank was considered successful by the project members is the fact that the regional

administrative partners were able to draw on previous work in the selection of actors. Second, it was also this experience that led to a particular framing of the think tank:

“I told them that if we want to have impact we need that think tank. That was, it has been a like a process. For the think tank we selected stakeholders that were already somehow engaged in the work I was doing and that could have some relation to citizen science and we open it a little bit more also.” (interview, Generalitat informant)

The think tank in this framing was a process to select not only pilot activities but also to build and stabilize relationships with actors from the Catalan R&I ecosystem. As such it built on previously established links and was a means to make use of those.

The reason why the Generalitat needed a project like TRANSFORM for this is – as one actor from the administration told us – that in order to be able to do things differently, there is always the need for some mandate, “it’s an opportunity also to start talking” (interview). A project like TRANSFORM then is described as an opportunity or “umbrella” to do this kind of nurturing work within the administration. And this nurturing – doing something “different” – reaches beyond the administration and also includes understandings and translations of citizen science of the different partners in the pilot activities.

The fostering and nurturing of the relationships depend, however, on keeping them interested while keeping them on track, not by offering easy money or other resources but by insisting on the underlying cause, whether it be formulated as transformative change, RRI or citizen empowerment. And it is in this context the insistence on challenges being “real” makes sense: “Real” here means meaningful for the local actors in their local context and, in the words of one informant, that it connects “with something that is already happening in the territory”.

We shall later discuss the enormous contrast between the TRANSFORM experience and the kind of RRI work that happens in its original context, namely that of biotechnology and converging sciences and technologies (see chapter 8). Also, before the introduction of the acronym of RRI, the basic challenge of public engagement with what is typically thought of as technoscience is to anchor it in people's lived context. Projects such as TRANSFORM indicate a very different trajectory for the RRI concept, namely that of anchoring it in places and life-worlds, in the concerns of citizens whose health care needs are not met and of public servants who worry about the insufficient waste separation in their municipality. Without this anchor, no actual transformation will take place. Or at least, this is the hypothesis.

The actual transformations taking place may look small from the outside: the doctors and the endometriosis patients at Hospital Sant Pau begin to talk to each other in a different way. At the city hall of Mollet, technicians and other civil servants establish a new form of dialogue. Students, school pupils, family members and neighbours begin to talk together about recycling of waste. The sum of these place-based, local activities contributes to the overall momentum of RIS3CAT's mission and to the visibility and reputation of citizen science in Catalonia because they generate some new witnesses and ambassadors and extend the networks.

It is a truism among researchers with a lot of experience with EU-funded projects that in EU projects, people "do what they do". One may have to promise novelty and radical departure from one's business as usual. At the level of practice, however, with the limits on time and money that are usually quite strict, most partners in such projects will play it safe and do what they are best at and have done many times before. What we are presenting in this chapter, may be seen as an argument in favour of, if not conservatism, at least the value of maintenance, continuity, and care work in a time where the rhetoric of novelty and disruption is strong. The TRANSFORM project as it was conducted was not framed as something completely new or as something that is expected to initiate something entirely novel. Much rather, it was part of a long lineage of activities, it is an enabler of sorts, that makes it possible for actors in the Catalan R&I ecosystem to actually try to do "something more". To do so, they crucially depend on work that is done by the project team before and after the actual project. One colleague from an administrative partner stated that "it never works if you build things from nowhere".

The lines of continuity, from before and well after the project, are also what matters when the individual partners are to assess what they gained from the project. In our conversations in the basement, the expression "it is more than that" emerged again and again. For Science for Change, TRANSFORM was more than the pilots and more than achieving the project objectives in the sense that it opened up new arenas and ventures for citizen science in the future. For the Generalitat, TRANSFORM was one of many pieces in its puzzle, another opportunity tailored to continue on the larger mission of transforming the Catalan R&I ecosystem and indeed improve Catalan society. And for the Open Systems Group, it was both of these things but also another small experiment in real time to simultaneously study and take part in what happens when people's agency is strengthened in unconventional ways, in an open social system where ultimately the demarcation between "science" and "society" becomes less of an issue.

Chapter 6 – Regional development and co-design in the Brussels-Capital Region

Co-design and DIY in the centre of Brussels

The first impression before even entering the actual office space of Be Participation is the sheer number of various things, installations, and apparatuses in the entry hall. Traces of past engagements and materialized plans of issues to be discussed and debates to come. There is a clear Do-It-Yourself feeling to this place. Once inside this impression only becomes stronger as one sees an open space with tables, white boards, some desks here and there, pens, sheets of paper and easily movable furniture like chairs and desks. This is clearly a space that signals the aim to be flexible and adaptive to different publics-in-the-making, a space that rejects being limited to one particular “Anordnung”, Martina Löw’s notion for the social orderings that are manifest in the material set-up of spaces (Löw, 2001). As such, the material set-up affords certain activities and ways of interacting (Gibson, 1977).

As such the Be Participation offices are clearly different from what we experienced in Lombardy when entering the history-laden halls of Fondazione Giannino Bassetti in the centre of Milan with its walls of books and expensive wooden furniture which embody the longstanding collaboration with the regional administration and the strong ties between FGB and the Lombardian R&I policymaking elites. Instead, the Be Participation space speaks to a DIY community, bottom-up initiatives, and different forms of multi-stakeholder engagement. This is the point of departure from which our colleagues in the Brussels-Capital Region cluster design and conduct their activities and translate RRI into a dynamic and ever-changing research and innovation ecosystem.

Design Thinking & Multi-Stakeholder Engagement

One of the central pillars of the work of the Brussels Capital region cluster is design thinking. The practice of designing is mostly associated with making technologies or products aesthetically pleasing and thus more attractive to users and consumers. Towards the end of the last century design thinking became prominent within management debates, business circles and in the consulting community. People like IBM’s Thomas Watson Jr. or Apple’s Steve Jobs have referred to design thinking when describing their work. Design

thinking is also institutionally well-established, for example in the d.school at Stanford University or in the School for Design Thinking at the Hasso Platter Institute in Potsdam (Carlgren et al., 2016). In an article in the Harvard Business Review from 2008 Tim Brown – chair and CEO of IDEO, one of the main proponents of design thinking – describes design thinking as follows:

“Put simply, it is a discipline that uses the designer’s sensibility and methods to match people’s needs with what is technologically feasible and what a viable business strategy can convert into customer value and market opportunity.” (Brown, 2008, p. 2)

This description shows that in the view of its proponents there is more to design thinking than its aesthetic dimension. It is about considering consumer-needs and integrating them into product design. Proponents of design thinking thus consider themselves to be problem solvers that are not only useful in making things aesthetically nice at the end of the production process but should rather be part of the innovation process from the very beginning.

Famously – or perhaps also infamously – design thinkers distinguish different phases. While Brown and Katz (Brown & Katz, 2011) initially talk about “three spaces of innovation” – inspiration, ideation and implementation – these spaces are later developed into five modes: the empathize mode, the define mode, the ideate mode, the prototype mode, and the test mode. The empathize mode includes research and data collection with the aim to understand the user perspective and experience. The define mode builds on that research and is about the creation of a shared problem framing including the desired outcomes and potential constraints. The ideate mode focuses on developing solutions for that problem, preferably as many solutions as possible so there is material to experiment with. Finally, the prototype and test modes focus on producing tangible solutions that are tested with potential users. The crucial thing for design thinkers here is to produce something tangible, artifacts that can be tested and toyed with (Wolcott et al., 2021; Wolcott & McLaughlin, 2020). Often, these designs include so-called “sacrificial concepts”, early ways of capturing user experiences that can later on be abandoned easily. The idea is to elicit strong reactions from the users to spark debate and potentially (supplemental or alternative) ideas.

More recently, Jon Kolko in his article “Design thinking comes of age” (Kolko, 2015) argued that design thinking has moved beyond being a method for product design and is on its way to develop into a set of principles that can shape corporate cultures. The core

elements in this process are a organization-wide focus on user experience and emotions, a reliance on creating models and artifacts to examine complex problems, the use prototypes to develop potential solutions, a tolerance of failure and a willingness to nurture a culture that is based on iterative processes. Importantly, a key pillar in design thinking as a culture is to exhibit restraint in the sense of focusing on the creation of a simple emotional value of certain products. Some proponents of design thinking argue that the focus on consumer experiences needs to be supplemented with an increased attention towards the needs and experiences of communities (Meroni & Fassi, 2013; Meroni & Sangiorgi, 2011). In doing so the principles of design thinking are brought together with participatory approaches and action research for community development.

Over the years, the ideas expressed by proponents of design thinking have been criticized both among designers but also from innovation scholars and engagement practitioners. Sometimes these criticisms are formulated in quite drastic ways. Historian of science Lee Vinsel for example published a text with the title “Design thinking is kind of like syphilis — it’s contagious and rots your brains”.⁶ Another article asks: “Design Thinking is Bullsh*t”.⁷

There are two main lines of criticism that go something like this: first, what is often described as design thinking is an assemblage of vague terms without any clear meaning or pointers towards actual practice. It is a fad made up of buzzwords that can be filled with meaning and don’t offer anything new beyond what people already know and like. As Vinsel describes it, “floating balloons of jargon, full of hot air”. The second line of critique in a sense defends this vagueness of the terms and points to the iterative and experimental nature of design thinking and argues that it is the simplification of design thinking into methodologies, into linear step-by-step guides that is the problem (in order to package it into sellable products). What is intended to be an iterative process of tinkering and experimenting has been streamlined into a step-by-step guides that are premised on linear processes. This is visible in papers that propose a series of steps or a number of tips to stimulate design thinking processes (Wolcott et al., 2021). The problem then is not so much the approach itself, but its marketing as a silver bullet solution to all problems. This is also captured in a definition of design thinking, which Natasha Jen proposed in her talk “Design Thinking is Bullsh*t”:

⁶ <https://sts-news.medium.com/design-thinking-is-kind-of-like-syphilis-its-contagious-and-rots-your-brains-842ed078af29>. Accessed November 17, 2022.

⁷ <https://99u.adobe.com/videos/55967/natasha-jen-design-thinking-is-bullshit>. Accessed November 17, 2022.

“Design Thinking packages a designer’s way of working for a non-design audience by way of codifying design’s processes into a prescriptive, step-by-step approach to creative problem solving – claiming that it can be applied by anyone to any problem.” (Natasha Jen)

The solution for people within the design thinking community is to resist the urge to create an overly simplistic version of design thinking for the sake of popularity and instead focus on the experimental and iterative nature of the design thinking process. This, however, leaves open the question of what is actually new about it and where the added value of design thinking actually lies. Despite this criticism, design thinking is still widely used also beyond the United States in Europe as visible e.g. in the work of Politecnico di Milano’s School of Design⁸ or the DESIS Network.⁹

The Brussels Capital region cluster, in addition to making use of design thinking concepts and tools also uses a version of multi-stakeholder engagement. In doing so, our colleagues draw on work promoting the inclusion of actors from the so-called “quadruple helix” (Leydesdorff, 2012). Basically, the quadruple-helix models is a way to describe innovation governance as the interaction between actors from the university-industry-government, and the public. Sometimes there is even talk about a quintuple helix, which in addition aims at including the environment as an extra actor. These concepts were developed by Carayannis and Campbell (2010) and build on the initial work of Etzkowitz and Leydesdorff (1998).

This, while the inflation of helices may sound somewhat abstract, cerebral or even off-putting, there is actually a genealogy behind it that reaches back to the closing decades of the previous century. These are debates about changing modes of producing and circulating knowledge, captured in terms such as “Mode 2” or “post-normal science”. In this context, the notion of a “triple helix” was developed (Etzkowitz & Leydesdorff, 1998) and subsequently attracted interest within the ongoing discussions about changing relations between (academic) science, administrations, industry and publics or civil society. Initially, the triple helix model was developed as a heuristic for analysing changing relations between academy, industry and government, whereas Mode 2 (and probably to a lesser extent also post-normal science) also can be seen as a diagnosis about ongoing developments. As a heuristic it aims at directing attention to the relations between

⁸ <https://www.design.polimi.it/en/>. Accessed November 17, 2022.

⁹ <https://www.desisnetwork.org/>. Accessed November 17, 2022.

universities, industries, and governmental actors in innovation processes. The starting point, however, is the assumption that a transition is occurring that renders university-industry-government relations increasingly important for contemporary knowledge societies (Leydesdorff & Etzkowitz, 2001). This, while one of the core interests of Etzkowitz and Leydesdorff are indeed changing ways of producing and circulating knowledge, they very much bring in an institutional perspective. Innovation scholars have therefore noted that their work “is focused on the organizational context of Mode 2 research” (Hellström & Jacob, 2000, p. 76).

By why use the analogy of a helix? The reason for this is actually quite simple: by using the picture of a helix they aim at stressing processes of iterative interactions between universities, industries and government actors and the production and governance of innovation. In addition, the metaphor of a spiral movement also points to an element of reflexivity. Introducing the helix model can thus be understood as a critique of simplistic linear models of innovation.

What makes this relevant for work within RRI pilot projects is that in discussions about helices of different actors participatory and collaborative ways of working play an important role. Where the post-normal science debate argues for engaging an “extended peer community” that includes people that are potentially affected or even negatively impacted by certain technoscientific innovations or policy decisions, Helga Nowotny – one of the main proponents of the Mode 2 literature - argues that so-called “transdisciplinary” modes of knowledge production can lead to more “socially robust knowledge” (Nowotny, 2003). This interest in quality and robustness goes together with a call for “accountability” of science and innovation that is also a crucial element of RRI.

“Social accountability permeates the whole knowledge production process. It is reflected not only in interpretation, and diffusion of results but in the definition of the problem and the setting of research priorities, as well.” (Gibbons, 1994, p. 62)

The triple-, quadruple-, and quintuple-helix models therefore share a certain concern with debates about Mode 2 and post-normal science, which is the ambition to initiate epistemic, social, political, and also moral re-orderings. In some of the scholarly literature from the last decade, these concerns are captured in notions such of responsibility and care (Arora et al., 2020; Mol, 2008; Maria Puig de la Bellacasa, 2011; María Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017).

In what follows, we will carve out the particular translation of RRI into the Brussels-Capital Region research and innovation ecosystem and into approaches guided by design-thinking and quadruple-helix multi-stakeholder engagement.

The pilot projects – a brief introduction

There were two pilot activities in the part of the TRANSFORM project conducted in the Brussels-Capital Region (BCR). RRI was here translated in two quite distinct ways: first, as an urban development project that sets out to deal with the problem of unsold food, and second as quadruple-helix engagements following a design thinking approach with young researchers at the Catholic University of Louvain.

Unsold food

This pilot activity addressed the issue of how to deal with unsold food in the Brussels Capital region, an issue that was being addressed by local citizen-led initiatives, not-for-profit and for-profit organizations. At the time, there were several different initiatives addressing the challenge of food waste in Brussels that were in competition with each other. The cluster partners Be Participation and INNOVIRIS organized engagement activities to co-design pathways towards solving this issue. The general aim of RRI as it was translated in the BCR cluster's work, was to provide a service or to give support to publics already formed around a certain issue.

“It’s this project called No Javel! that is a citizen initiative, so it is completely unstructured. It is it exists as a non-for-profit thing, association, but it’s totally handled by volunteers, citizens and they go and get tons and tons and tons of unsold products from organic supermarkets, only organic places and they redistribute it to poor people.” (Int_09)

This stance resonates with Callon and Rabeharisoa's idea of “the wild” and with work from Noortje Marres on the simultaneous formation of publics and issues. The pilot engaged with locally situated knowledge and lived experiences of food production and consumption systems combined with social innovation for groups described as "disadvantaged" and "people who don't feel entitled or interested" to participate in political processes. So, what we see is a clear normative stance in the objective to contribute to an improvement of regional governance approaches.

The ethos of “being of service” – a central pillar of what it means to do “good engagement” in this case and also a translation of the idea of R&I becoming responsive to or aligned with society - is crucial here. In the Unsold Food pilot this meant, for example, identifying needs and building networks, a version of responsibility that focuses on "facilitating meaningful engagement" with regional bottom-up initiatives focused on social innovation.

Simultaneously, the pilot aimed to be useful for the project partner from the regional administration. This particular idea of service we see here – focused on the “sustainability” of the initiative – managed to integrate INNOVIRIS into this translation. For INNOVIRIS a central concern is the longevity of the initiatives they fund: this, then, is simultaneously about the initiative and maintenance of local RRI projects. Thus, the idea is a twofold one: on the one hand to help solve the problems by facilitating “meaningful engagement”, and on the other hand to find ways to avoid such situations by influencing the evaluation grid at INNOVIRIS in a way that makes it sensitive to such issues.

During the first half of the year 2022, the Brussels cluster planned and organized a series of workshops in which a range of actors with stakes in the unsold food issue were involved to discuss and deliberate. The cluster organized four workshops with citizens and app users (Too Good to Go, Phenix, Happy Hours Market), group interviews with customers of a social grocery store, a workshop with representatives of associations providing food aid from unsold food, a workshop with representatives of public authorities concerned by the flow of unsold food, and individual interviews with representatives of Happy Hours Market, Too Good to Go, DREAM, Färm, Sequoia and Bio c’Bon. Overall, they involved 50 citizens (“users”), 6 representatives of local and regional public authorities and funding bodies, more than 15 representatives of local associations (non-profit), innovation representatives, representatives of retailers and supermarkets and the private sector, as well as circular economy experts.

In October 2022, the cluster organized a sharing workshop to reflect on the common points identified and to start developing possible solutions as well as proposals for possible next steps in the process

AcquaSens and Algorella - Working with Innovators at UC Louvain

The second pilot in BCR focused on practices of co-designing innovations, specifically on the development of water sensors (AcquaSens) and in the broader area of circular economy (Algorella). Here, the consortium partners BeParticipation and the Catholic University of Louvain worked together with PhD students on their projects and innovations.

RRI here took the form of design-thinking in so-called quadruple helix workshops. RRI thus got translated into a network of BeParticipation (a civil society organisation), a university and PhD committees, students and their innovation projects, selected actors from civil society, industry, and academia, INNOVIRIS, and potential evaluation mechanisms at (potentially) several levels. These quadruple helix workshops constituted a form of organized and guided deliberation. There were several interdependent and entwined aims which included (1) discussing the political issues involved in the innovations, (2) a process of collaborative prototyping, (3) feedback on the marketability of the innovation as a product, and finally (4) a showcase of the Spheres protocols (we will return to that point in the next section)

These activities were explicitly discussed by the actors as a form “upstream engagement” organized over a long span of time on several occasions with different foci. In them, the figure of the “innovator” is crucial. Innovators are developers of a certain product to be. At the same time, however, they are PhD students primarily concerned with research. Their PhD research brings in a particular idea of innovation that resonates with RRI principles, which is the concept of a “360 degree view of innovation”. RRI translated as quadruple helix engagement here is explicitly linked to Jasanoff’s idea of “technologies of humility” (Jasanoff, 2003).

Interestingly, while the partners in this pilot argued strongly in favour of the integration of heterogenous actors into innovation processes, there was also a palpable attentiveness to the “risks” of such engagements and a sensitivity to the need to protect PhD students and their projects to a certain degree. We observed a careful demarcation or purification work on the side of the researchers. There are areas where engagement is “not interesting” (Int_12), e.g. in “highly technological” (Int_12) areas where also simple models of knowledge transfer work. Thus, we see a simultaneous processes of entanglement and purification. Citizens appear in multiple roles: they appear as providers of valuable feedback for the innovators that can help to improve the innovators work, but they also seen as posing some risk to these projects. That is, there is a risk and potential for the projects to get in “trouble”, for example if the citizens negatively evaluate a PhD-project. We will return to that point later.

What we see in the BCR cluster thus are two distinct translations of RRI, one focusing very much on co-creation and community-based needs and goals (Ludwig & Macnaghten, 2019), the other centred around changing innovation cultures in the education of engineers at universities.

The BCR ecosystem – Contingency and Uncertainty

The organizational set-up in the Brussels-Capital Region cluster provides a contrast to the Lombardy and Catalonia clusters. Where the latter can start from already established and relatively stable relations between the research and administrative partners and can develop their activities from that starting point, our colleagues from the BCR cluster basically started from scratch. What we observe in this cluster therefore is a case in which RRI gets translated into a regional R&I ecosystem in the absence of certain kinds of relationships. The interesting question then becomes what this means for RRI work and its impact.

In the conversations we conducted with the different project partners from this cluster, the general situation in the R&I ecosystem was framed as fragmented and “complex” (Int_11) by both the research as well as the partners from the regional administration. Furthermore, research and innovation system in the Brussels-Capital region is perceived as being in “constant movement” (Int_09) or likened to a “cycle” (Int_09) of the different actors. For the non-administrative partners this made it difficult to assess who might be relevant collaborators:

“So, there’s this constant movement of, because they are all functionaries, so civil servants. So basically, there were some of the people who were in the ministry ended up in Innoviris. Some of the people who were in Innoviris ended up in the in the government. So, there is constant cycle.” (Int_09)

The central challenge then was one of deciphering this particular R&I ecosystem and to find or create possibilities for RRI inspired pilot activities. Another challenge of the dynamic situation in the administrative part of this cluster and the R&I ecosystem more generally was to identify the issues that could be addressed through RRI approaches. Given this dynamic situation, topics and priorities tended to shift constantly. Overall, the activities in the BCR cluster are described as being more “disconnected” (Int_09) compared to what was done in Lombardy and Catalonia. These difficulties were already visible to some extent in the process of designing and planning the project in the proposal stage, where a range of different administrative partners were considered at different points in time. The decision that INNOVIRIS would be a partner in this cluster was made only at the very end of the process. They themselves talk about their involvement in the project as “accidental” (Int_11). The standing of the research partner in this cluster also is different compared to the other clusters. Be Participation describe themselves as relative “newcomers” (Int_09) within the BCR research and innovation ecosystem.

What this case shows then, are translations of RRI that co-emerge with the specificities of the R&I ecosystem and the position the pilot activities take within them. Interestingly, this

also makes visible a different kind of maintenance work; one that aims at building trust and identifying niches for constructive RRI activities.

One of the core ideas for how to address this situation in the BCR cluster is to develop a so-called “protocol”, which is intended to help actors from the R&I ecosystem to assess innovation projects and consult them on how to best incorporate RRI principles. This was called the “Spheres protocol”. RRI here takes the shape of a set of “techniques” or “scripts”. The intention then is to enable it to “travel” across different sites, actors and even sectors. Necessarily this also implies a certain degree of standardization. Conceptualized like this, the Spheres protocol is able to solve a number of issues that are specific to this cluster: it can travel to a university setting and be used to introduce students to a more holistic view of innovation. Also, it is imagined becoming part of evaluation procedures at INNOVIRIS. In a sense, it is intended to become a kind of boundary object to debate and further develop innovation models through the evaluation infrastructures in place.

In our conversations the colleagues from the BCR cluster talked about the “Spheres” pilot as a “protocol”, a “prism”, a “service” or a “vehicle”. What this means is that it was intended to be applied as a lens for analysis and as a set of guiding principles that can be used to give input to these projects. Spheres, framed like this, is about “first analysing what could be interesting to bring to the project from the RRI like tools and then organize some activities based on the need that we have identified” (Int_10)

As such it would become a service for researchers which ideally would support them in considering issues that they had not previously thought of – always through the incorporation of RRI principles. There is thus an element of research and analysis, but always as a service, never as an end in itself. As such the objective to create such a protocol as an overarching activity is a translation of RRI that is clearly shaped by the specific situation and R&I ecosystem the BCR cluster partners are working with.

Translating RRI in the BCR cluster pilot activities

“Good” engagement in the Brussels-Capital Region cluster

More than in any of the other clusters, the Brussels Capital region (BCR) cluster is characterised by a diverse set of translations of RRI. RRI is translated as 4-helix workshops, as co-design process to improve PhD students’ innovation together with their understanding of the concept innovation itself, and as a way to improve the evaluation

criteria of an R&I funding agency. As such the ideas about what RRI is range from community development to an approach to research and even research evaluation.

These translations become visible in answers to the question “what constitutes ‘good’ engagement?” These answers differ in terms of the underlying models of engagement, the general aims and purposes, the subject positions available to different actors, and in regard to the position of the activities on the imagined continuum between RRI as community development or as a form of research. There are also interesting differences in how different project partners think about the impacts of their activities and the temporality of their activities.

What is striking is that these different translations of RRI as engagement are mediated by the networks people build and by their position within these networks. RRI as practiced by an NGO is – perhaps unsurprisingly so – very different from RRI done within a university or a funding agency. The interesting question will be how exactly they are different.

Now, what does this mean in practice?

To start with, in Brussels cluster we encounter several different pilot activities with different – equally legitimate – translations of RRI. As we have briefly outlined above there is a collaboration on the issue of unsold food, work with PhD students from UC Louvain on water sensors and food innovations, work towards integration of RRI principles with INNOVIRIS and the transversal work on the pilot called “Spheres”.

In what follows we will describe the different translations of RRI that become visible through these pilot activities and the way in which our colleagues make sense of them. The overarching approach that was intended to guide these pilot activities was the so-called Spheres protocol, sometimes referred to as the “pilot of pilots” by our colleagues from Brussels. And that’s where we want to start our story.

SPHERES – the pilot of pilots

The Spheres pilot is – or was intended to be – the overarching methodology through which the different activities, partners, and versions of RRI are integrated. Spheres is a set of protocols that transverse the different groups within the cluster. RRI and engagement gets translated as a methodology, a set of “techniques” or “scripts” that are both a process and a heuristic. As such, Spheres is conceptualised as a tool for analysing R&I projects from an RRI-inspired perspectives and provide the means to improve the RRI elements in such

projects. Ideally, from the perspective of the BCR cluster partners, the Spheres protocols can become a tool that has the ability to “travel” across different sites and sectors, something that can be provided from one actor to another, which necessarily implies an objective of standardization.

This is the “pilot of pilots” for the BCR cluster. The initial idea was that all the different activities of the cluster are guided by the Spheres protocol and are also used to experiment with it and improve the prototype. Our colleagues talk about the Spheres pilot is described as a “protocol” but also as a “prism”, a “service” or a “vehicle”. As such it is intended to be used as a lens for analysis and then also as a set of guiding principles according to which to give input to these projects:

“[F]irst analysing what could be interesting to bring to the project from the RRI like tools and then organize some activities based on the need that we have identified to, yeah. To support like and in the case of the water sensor project for example, it was done through the organization of workshops, citizen workshops.” (Int_10)

Spheres thus resonates with the cluster’s notion of RRI as a service. This would mainly be a service for researchers and help them to take issues into account that they did not previously consider.

“And what is interesting is basically what we tried to also explain to the researcher is that you can develop a very nice innovation that will measure the quality of water but if you don’t pay attention to the perception that citizen have, you, they will maybe they will say okay, fine, I can test the quality but I will still use the bottled water. So, you have to understand if your innovation like replies also to a need or to so/ or if they/ otherwise it can be completely disconnected from society and so yeah.” (Int_10)

While this description of the Spheres pilot clearly resonates with an ethos of RRI as providing a service, there is also a strong element of research and analysis using RRI principles. This analysis is always a means for a service to be provided, never an end in itself.

The Sphere process consists of three main steps: (1) the definition of the project problem and needs, (2) the creation of an action plan, (3) and the implementation of the action plan through a series of activities. This is where the influence of design-thinking is most clearly visible in that it promotes prototyping, and centres around the users of the innovations to

be. The first phase of the Spheres protocol is akin to the empathize mode in design thinking. It is also here that citizens – in the form of quadruple-helix actors – should be involved in the definition of the problem and the development of the innovations. RRI enters to process as assessment criteria in relation to gender, ethics, open access, public engagement, and science education. Participatory processes and attention to these RRI dimensions were also envisioned in the development and implementation of the Spheres action plans. In the implementation phase the role of the citizens is to discuss potential ethical social and environmental issues and, in that way, to validate ideas.

Given this use of the Spheres protocol as an overarching or transversal pilot, some of the activities are also devoted to tinkering or experimenting with these protocols. Additionally, in addition to attempts of mainstreaming principles of RRI, also the Spheres protocols are being showcased in order to proof the added value of this (mainly for the innovators).

At one point during the project the Brussels cluster launched a call for project proposals using the Spheres approach. The idea was to find projects that could go through the process, be assessed, and advised against the principles outlined in the Spheres protocols. Unfortunately, there was not enough interest in this call for projects, so this process was stopped. Instead, our colleagues from Brussels got in contact with an initiative dealing with the issue of food waste and started developing what would become the pilot project on unsold food.

Unsold Food and the ethos of “being of service”

As we just described, one of the main RRI activities in Brussels was the work on the issue of unsold food. This work is premised on a particular translation of RRI with its own ideas about engagement and the actors that need to be involved for what purposes. The basic idea about the purpose of engaging citizens is expressed by one of the organizers of these activities:

“It’s this project called No Javel! that is a citizen initiative so it is completely unstructured. It is it exists as a non-for-profit thing, association, but it’s totally handled by volunteers, citizens and they go and get tons and tons and tons of unsold products from organic supermarkets, only organic places and they redistribute it to poor people.” (Int_09)

Our colleague here talks about one of the actors in the unsold food area in Brussels - No Javel! – and what makes this initiative a relevant actor for this kind of work. There are two

main points that stand out in her description: first, this is about an issue that is relevant for citizens right now as it brings together environmental concerns with questions of social justice. Second, it is important for her that this initiative is created by citizens themselves. It is “volunteers” who work on improving the ways in which unsold food is dealt with because it actually matters to them and their personal lives.

“So, basically what’s interesting in this project is that completely bottom-up approach. So, it’s a project that was created and that is managed completely by citizens. It’s not that it’s a project that is answering a call for projects or a specific funding. It’s really an initiative coming from citizens (...) and it’s basically a lady that was homeless and - I don’t know if she was homeless but in a very preca/ how do you say that word.” (Int_10)

RRI thus takes on elements of community development as our colleagues get involved with this initiative to show ways of how to solve the problems that emerge when several actors with different priorities start working on the issue of unsold food.

The general aim of RRI framed like this is to provide a service or to give support to publics already formed around a certain issue. This means that we are dealing with a form of uninvited participation (Wynne, 2011). This stance also resonates with work from Noortje Marres on the simultaneous formation of publics and issues (Marres, 2007). It sits also well within an ethos of PNS that is concerned with extended peer communities. What these authors argue is that it is important to be attentive to how publics are formed and that citizen engagement projects can have the effect to create publics through their activities that don’t exist independently from them. Publics that could to some extent be described as “artificial”. This can have the problematic effect that – once the project and funding are over – these publics disappear again. In that way, working with initiatives like the ones involved in the unsold food pilot project can also be seen as a response to a major shortcoming of many such initiatives, which is that very often publics get formed top-down through engagement events or self-select due to socio-economic status (they have the education and spare time to do so). Importantly, working with initiatives that already exist prior to the engagement activities increase the chance of a life after the event for these groups and the issues they discuss. But it is not only the publics but also the issues themselves that are shaped by how citizen engagement is set up and organized. When citizens are engaged that are already organized as an initiative this also means that they

have their own understanding of the issue at hand which might be different from the understanding of the public authorities.

But most importantly, engaging with initiatives like No Javel! also makes sure that locally situated knowledge and the lived experiences of food production and consumption systems can become part of the formulation of policies.

These themes are also important for our colleagues who worked on these pilot projects. In the conversations we had, these groups of citizens were often referred to as "disadvantaged publics" and "people who don't feel entitled or interested" to participate in political processes.

"So I thought well, you know one of the biggest challenges that we have in the activities we do is to involve disadvantaged publics and people who don't feel entitled or interested for different reasons they don't. So we thought okay, this could be a really nice collaboration. So I told them, look. I can what I can do on my side is bringing to the association activities and projects that are, can generate this meaningful engagement of the type of target audiences that you can mobilise around the association but it's going to be on the topics that are familiar to me so it's going to be about science, technology and innovation." (Int_09)

Those of course are also people who wouldn't usually sign up for a focus group on food production and consumption systems. What we see in this translation of RRI is a clear normative stance expressed in the objective to engage with people who have actual agency and clear interests in order to contribute to an improvement of regional governance approaches.

This ethos of being of "service" is a central pillar of what it means to do "good engagement" in this pilot project. It also describes the underlying model of the relation between the project partners and the actors they engage with. This ethos expresses a version of the RRI idea in which research and innovation systems are supposed to become (more) responsive to or better aligned with society. In the Unsold Food pilot project this means to engage with pre-existing initiatives in order to make room for their understanding of the issues. This also means for example identifying needs and building networks.

What we see here is therefore a version of responsibility that focuses on "facilitating meaningful engagement" with regional bottom-up initiatives focused on social innovation.

“And what so what was interesting for us is the fact that it’s coming from citizens completely and we wanted to suggest to them this service that I was explaining before that what we decided to implement in the cluster here in Brussels to basically bring some representative from the different Helix of the Quadruple Helix and to reflect a bit on the governance maybe of this initiative to see how it could be sustained.” (Int_10)

This particular idea of service we see here – focused on the “sustainability” of the initiative – manages to integrate also INNOVIRIS into this translation. For INNOVIRIS, a central concern is the longevity of the initiatives they fund: this then is simultaneously about the initiative and maintenance of local RRI projects.

One important feature of this particular translation of RRI and its model of engagement is a focus on contentious issues. While lots of work in the context of deliberative democracy has the tendency to steer debates towards finding consensus (Felt & Fochler, 2010; Turnhout et al., 2010), the issue of unsold food is characterized by increasing tensions between the different parties involved. While some of the actors are grounded in civil society others have an economic interest in mind. In this pilot project, two or more parties are doing something that seemingly contributes to the "public good". In doing so, however, they actually get in conflict with each other. Instead of "co-benefits" there are unforeseen negative consequences.

“So they you get yeah food that is about to expire less expensive but this happy hour market even has a specific aspect that is they tend to give it especially to poor, to poor people. (...) So this has reduced their access to unsold products of good quality. So they are in conflict with these things that are supposed to do good. So in principle they are all against gaspillage, against throwing things away that are still eatable and sometimes even social aspect of support in those in need. They’ve managed to be conflicting with each other on flux on a flux of, of certain products.” (Int_09)

It thus comes as no surprise that the partners in this cluster are at times pushed into a position of mediators, a position which they refused due to the limit capacities of this pilot (we will come back to the challenges that come with organizing such engagements as pilots later).

The idea is then of twofold one: on the one hand the idea indeed is to help solve the tensions at hand. This is imagined to be achieved by facilitating “meaningful engagement” and in doing so giving a showcase of how such a process can work to the actors involved. On the other hand, the pilot project also is intended to speak to INNOVIRIS in that it aims at developing ways to avoid such situations in the future. One way to do this is by initiating discussions about re-framing the evaluation grid at INNOVIRIS in a way that makes it sensitive to such issues.

Thus, this translation of RRI with its particular model of engagement manages to enrol INNOVIRIS because it resonates with practices that are already implemented at INNOVIRIS and also with challenges that are relevant for INNOVIRIS. While it may not be in TRANSFROM’s project lifetime that these discussions will become consequential at INNOVIRIS, this issue is not at least registered within INNOVIRIS.

This model of engagement as support to bottom-up civil society initiatives is seen as addition to a more prevalent model that focuses on engagement as technology transfer. One of the actors from the Brussels cluster explains this model through talking about so-called “technology transfer offices”, which are basically people paid by INNOVIRIS to make connections to universities:

“So for example Innoviris has in all Brussels universities they have this called TTOs, so technology transfer offices and all these technology transfer offices within the universities have one person paid by Innoviris there that works there. So they are really on the technology transfer side. So in a way yes it’s normal that they work with the private sector more. So of course collaboration of research pri/ public-private collaboration for sure. But to me it’s still a bit surprising that the, the civil society part is completely mi/ absent let’s say because in the end lots of these applications whether they are then, they come to life in the Belgium or Brussels territory or anywhere else” (Int_09)

Therefore, from this perspective engagement is very much framed in terms of university-industry collaborations and there is room for improvement when it comes to bringing in actors from civil society. Some actors working on the pilot activities of the Brussels cluster argue that re-accentuating the model of engagement also means moving away from a narrow focus on “acceptance” as a purpose of engagement:

“And then he said that he used several times the word acceptance. So he said that this [N.N.], this guy from Co-create didn’t think that this mainstreaming in the end it comes back to the mainstreaming could bring more acceptance of research outcomes and innovations. So he said that he’s particularly interested in this concept and this thing about acceptance and that he would like to go deeper into what changes but works better when some projects (...) like innovations like we did with these water sensors do some type of participatory co-creation RRI.” (Int_09)

Our colleagues engaged in the Unsold Food pilot clearly work towards moving beyond a narrow understanding of acceptance, which frames rejection of policies or innovations in terms of a cognitive or information deficit. And indeed, such a stance points to important differences between enhancing the acceptability of an innovation by means of public debate about framings and (collectively imagined) ends and using engagement as a means for manufacturing acceptance. We will come back to this issue in the cluster-comparison).

For now, we will turn to the other partners in this cluster and ask how they understand the activities they were involved in. In describing the model of engagement expressed in how the Unsold Food pilot project was set up and conducted, we already talked about the implicit other of that model. In a next step we will now move to INNOVIRIS and the Co-Create create program and to our assessment of how this relates to translations of RRI in TRANSFORM.

INNOVIRIS and the Co-Create model

INNOVIRIS is the regional administrative partner of BeParticipation and UC Louvain in the Brussels-Capital Region cluster. It is a public organization responsible for funding research and innovation on a regional level. As such INNOVIRIS occupies a distinct place within the regional R&I ecosystem that comes with a particular view on RRI, innovation governance and models of engagement. And while we see clear synergies in the collaboration between the different partners in this pilot, there are also some tensions between the model of RRI as a “service” that is expressed in the Unsold Food pilot with the work of INNOVIRIS.

From the perspective of INNOVIRIS responsible research and innovation is clearly an important idea. This idea, so we are told, is operationalized in one of their funding schemes named Co-Create. Similar to other colleagues from the BCR cluster, also within INNOVIRIS this program is described against the background of “technology transfer”. Technology transfer is seen as an outdated concept that we need to move beyond. So, in a sense RRI here is translated as a better version of technology transfer.

What is interesting here is that in our conversations the name Co-Create is described as a misnomer, since what is done in the projects funded in this “special scheme” is better thought of as “co-research”. Co-research describes two closely related ideas: first, there is the temporal argument that non-academic partners ought to be involved throughout the whole project duration, and second there is the socio-epistemic idea that they should be conceived as actors capable of providing substantive input:

“But it’s more co-research and what we expect is involvement in the research of all the partners. So not just saying one will do the action, one will do the implementation of the knowledge and the other one will generate the knowledge but everybody in the project should be co-researcher and it must include also citizens, academics, administration maybe, non-profit organizations, enterprises or whatever they want. But all these people should be involved in the research and to generate knowledge from the experiences and from their own knowledge. Complex.”
(Int_11)

This conceptualization then is to be understood as an explicit critique of the ideal of compartmentalization in projects and with a particular temporality implied in the notion of “transfer” when such activities are displaced to the end of a project. All of this, as our colleague from INNOVIRIS was keen to point out, should be happening throughout the project in a collaborative “travel”.

“And you have to do this, this travel all together and why is it so important, it’s because and that’s something we brought back a few weeks ago in TRANSFORM is how do we enter the knowledge transfer at the end of a participatory process. And in Co-Create it was also a question - and I discussed with my colleague a few weeks ago about that question - and for him you don’t have any knowledge transfer at the end of Co-Create because everything is done during the research process for all the necessary participant and the rest would not work and that’s a big problem. Knowledge transfer generally is quite difficult between university and the society. It’s difficult.” (Int_11)

What we see here is a rehearsal of one of the central ideas of RRI, which is that responsibility means upstream engagement, involvement of a broad range of actors early in the research and development process and not just at its end. As a successor of ELSI/ELSA research, it was an explicit aim of RRI to move the discussion of ethical, legal and social

aspects of research and innovation from an afterthought right at the beginning of research and innovation projects (Owen et al., 2012; von Schomberg, 2012).

Comments like these, however, are not just comments about RRI and co-creation, but in addition express a certain view about quality of participation and engagement practices more generally: early involvement, empowerment and agency are key issues in this strand of literature and criteria in the evaluation of citizen engagement activities (Wickson & Carew, 2014).

INNOVIRIS is very aware of the perceived risks and dangers of such a conceptualization of engagement. that this is scary for some actors.

“And also in Co-Create you give a certain power to the citizen to people that are not predictable. It’s easy to deal with academic experts when you have the, the, when you organise a lot of juries. It’s easy to deal with them. You know where they will going and you can predict what they will do and what they will decide. But with citizen we had a lot of surprise sometimes. You say, everybody say okay, this project is nice and then you, you have the citizen expert that say “I don’t give a shit about your project. It will not help anybody. You don’t know what’s our reality.” (Int_11)

Thinking about engagement of citizens in that way, our colleague points out, means re-thinking notions of power and agency and to relinquish some degrees of control. Becoming responsive to society, as RRI demands, introduces the possibility of unexpected outcomes. This will become an issue when we talk about the challenges of implementing RRI in doctoral education in the case of UC Louvain.

One way of dealing with “dangers” like this is to be very careful about the actual practice of empowerment, which means being cautious about which kinds of power to give to which citizens. There is thus an element of what could be called “top-down bottom-upping”.

“So, what could be also interesting for me - and I have not yet the vision - is how to find the citizens. That’s maybe also a big challenge because if you want to avoid professionalization of citizens, that’s one thing. If you want to avoid finding the citizens in the same pool of what we call “politicized citizens” so people that are active in associations is one. I don’t say it’s bad thing that they are involved in but if you consult them, they have already an orientation in the policies they want to defend. So that’s a difficulty for us, to find the right person.” (Int_11)

This model of engagement thus comes with a set of subject positions, ideas about what roles the citizens can play, which repertoires of interaction are available to them and which prior normative commitments they (are allowed to) bring into the engagement. This is described as the challenge to find “the right” persons. While it is difficult to describe who the right person might be, our colleague from INNOVIRIS here talks about “professionalized citizens” and “politicized citizens” as subject position that might be challenging. There are two main elements to this: these terms describe citizens who have pre-formed opinions and positions. These can relate to a particular policy or to a certain issue of contestation. In addition, there is some form of organization in the sense that there is a collective of citizens that exists independently from the engagement activities.

In addition, the professionalized and politicized citizens, the figure of the “concerned citizen” figures prominently in the account of our INNOVIRIS colleague. This figure comes into play especially in the ex-ante evaluation of projects at INNOVIRIS. The argument then is that is actually is a problem if the citizens who are evaluating project proposals are not “concerned”:

“So sometimes you have such a feedback from the citizen that tell you what do it's far from all consideration. “You tell us ah, we will make that all together but I don't give a shit of your things because I'm not concerned about it.” (Int_11)

This conceptualization of the role of citizens is in line with ideas of the importance of lived experience and “real-world problems” form discourses on transdisciplinarity. It also resonates with debates in the literature about matters of concern (Latour, 2004) and extended peer communities in post-normal science (Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1993). This is a very interesting conceptualization of citizens. Their involvement here is clearly not thought of as a source of data or embodiment of values (Irwin & Michael, 2003). Much rather this relates to the perceived quality of the research projects. Involving citizens in this way means moving beyond an idea of quality that focuses mainly on narrow ideas of excellence and instead aims at including the citizens ideas about relevance. When a project is able to meet the concerns of the citizens this means that there is some relevance. “Giving a shit” in this way becomes a quality criterion in terms of the local relevance of a project proposal.

Statements like this one perform an additional translation: global challenges and wicked problems are translated as local challenges in certain neighbourhoods. They need collaborative research because the people who have the lived experience of these problems need to contribute. Compared to the bottom-up character of the Unsold Food

pilot project, the model of collaboration present in the Co-Create funding scheme doesn't go as far in transferring power from researchers and innovators to citizens or "disadvantaged publics" as the other pilots do. As a consequence, there is still a danger that projects funded in this scheme are not able to adequately represent the lived experiences of the people in the region of interest.

This also says something about her idea of what "meaningful" engagement has to look like and what structural barriers are. Meaningful engagement in her view follows a logic of service or delivery and moves away from a logic of discovery, thus it is premised on a distinct translation of science-society relations. (From this perspective, funding programs that subtly favor work done in a logic of discovery can be seen as a structural barrier to RRI work in the regions.

There are still a number of open questions with this particular translation of RRI: what the residue of the idea of "technology transfer" is? How does this idea of transfer still linger within the Co-Create program if at all? And finally, how does the idea of responsible innovation governance go together with the aim of transfer?

RRI and working with "innovators" at UC Louvain

The third partner in the BCR cluster, the Catholic University of Louvain's Earth and Life Institute, works with PhD students in the broad area of circular economy. This pilot centres around practices of co-designing innovations in the area of water sensors (AcquaSens) and in relation to increasing the circularity of food production and consumption systems (Algorella). The TRANSFORM consortium partners BeParticipation and UC Louvain work together with PhD students on their projects and innovations.

This pilot represents another distinct line of work within this cluster. There are some similarities with what we described above, but also some key differences in how RRI is translated. These differences are connected to the particular site of the translation, doctoral education within a university. The overarching question for describing the work lead by UC Louvain then is how to integrate RRI into the education of engineering PhD students? What are the potentials and what are the risks?

RRI in this pilot is translated as so-called quadruple helix workshops. RRI thus gets woven into a very particular network of actors that is clearly distinct from the other pilots in the overall TRANSFORM project. It is therefore worthwhile to spend a little space to describe this network. First, we have BeParticipation, the cluster leader organized in the form of an

association; then there is UC Louvain, a university founded in 1834 that currently hosts around 30.000 students¹⁰ and considers itself to be the country's leading French-speaking university as well as the most international Belgian university; in addition there the university's PhD committees, the students and their innovation projects, selected actors from civil society, industry and academia, INNOVIRIS, and potential evaluation mechanisms at (potentially) several levels are part of this particular translation of RRI.

This combination of actors comes with a set of commitments and expectations which lead to a rather unique version of RRI focused on design thinking as an overarching approach to engagement, the ambition to impart a so-called "360-degree view of innovation" on the students, a particular idea of humility and the desire to safely guide PhD students through their projects. But let's start at the beginning.

The engagements in this pilot were organized a so-called 4-helix workshops. These are basically stakeholder workshops in which innovations are introduced and discussed with members from academia, politics, industry and (civil) society. As such this takes the form of an organized and guided deliberation. There were several workshops, the basic structure can be illustrated by going through the one of these workshops from the AquaSens project. The workshop addressed (1) the political issue of water use and plastic bottles in Brussels to contextualize the innovation at hand; it (2) contained a collaborative prototyping of a water sensor as well as (3) some input on the marketability of the sensor as a product; and (4) finally – this is specific to this being done in the context of a SwafS project in need of creating some sort of "impact" – a showcasing of the so-called Spheres protocols. This is a methodology to both analyse projects through the lens of RRI principles and to guide them towards becoming more aligned with these principles.

The issue of quality was very prominent in our conversations about these two projects, especially in regard to the education of PhD students and how they think about the innovation process. Good engagement here is discussed explicitly as a form of "upstream engagement". Different actors, in this view, need to be integrated in the process from early on. In addition, our colleagues talked about the importance of having such engagements or deliberations over a long span of time on several occasions with different foci.

¹⁰ <https://uclouvain.be/en/discover/faits-et-chiffres.html>. Accessed November 15, 2022.

One of the central figures in the accounts of our colleagues working on these projects was “the innovator”. Since this figure proved to be an important aspect of this particular translation of RRI, we want to devote some time to it.

Innovators are the developers of a certain product to be – in this case sensors to measure water quality or a food innovation. At the same time, however, they are also PhD students devoted to their own research and to finishing their PhD. This research they do in their PhDs brings in a particular idea of innovation that resonates with RRI principles. The main concept here is the idea of a “360-degree view of innovation”. This is a way of talking about RRI and engagement which is explicitly linked to the concept of a “technology of humility” as developed by Sheila Jasanoff (2003). She uses humility to challenge a particular model of the relationship between science and politics premised on the idea of “speaking truth to power”. What she calls “humility” means acknowledging the limits of scientific knowledge and knowing “when to stop turning to science to solve problems” (Jasanoff, 2007, p. 33). This stance is not to be confused with anti-scientism. Much to the contrary it is about being more reflexive about the role science should be playing when entering the field of politics. Some questions simply are not easily answered by science alone: “In the case of climate change, for example, science cannot tell us where and when disaster will strike, how to allocate resources between prevention and mitigation, which activities to target first in reducing greenhouse gases, or whom to hold responsible for protecting the poor. How should policymakers deal with these layers of ignorance?” (ibid.). Technologies of humility then are ways of dealing with different levels of uncertainty, ignorance, and indeterminacy by directing attention to framings, vulnerabilities, questions of distribution and potentials for collective learning. One way of doing so is re-thinking modes knowledge production and governance by integrating “extended peer communities” (Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1993) through different forms of engagement. This is also, how these ideas resonate with discussions about RRI in the BCR cluster and its pilot activities.

Our colleagues working on these pilots then argue for an early and continuous integration of a diverse set of actors with the aim to point to those questions that go beyond what a narrow focus on innovation as a mere technological artifact or product would unveil. There is a sense of openness to this approach, and this is also what our colleagues from UC Louvain talk about when they refer to a 360-degree view of innovation. While this is fully compatible with an RRI ethos, it is crucial to mention here is, that there is also a palpable attentiveness to the “risks” of such engagements. These risks are mainly expressed as a

sensitivity to the need to protect PhD students and their projects from an undue influence of other actors.

“So, we are really taking true research from the university. I am asking to some in that case it is two PHD students. I am in their PHD committee. I asked them to enter the process because I thought it was interesting for them, but we are taking a huge risk because we take true research, ongoing research and we enter them as example in our prototype, to test our prototype but that could fire us back to those students, OK. And that’s, you can see one of the students is today in the newspaper because of his work but it could really cause a lot of trouble if the experience in all prototypes is going wrong because you are testing something.” (Int_12)

In this quote a member of the project team who is at the same time part of the PhD committee of one of the innovators explains the risks of enrolling them into this “prototype” that is being tested. Actual ongoing research, so he argues, becomes part of an experiment in how to actually do research. Doing so comes with a set of risks that “could really cause a lot of trouble”. What we see expressed here is the ambition to expose the PhD students as innovators to the views and opinions of citizens and stakeholders and how this ambition is accompanied by the urge to be careful and protect the students and their project from potential harm. This protective drive then manifests in a form of demarcation or purification work on the side of the innovators. In their view there are areas where engagement is not “interesting”. Such areas are for example “highly technological” areas for which simple models of knowledge transfer work would provide a suitable means of engagement. Work on the circular economy for example is in need of input from the mining industry. So, through the subject position of “the innovator” and the perceived need to protect their work from harm we can see simultaneous processes of entanglement and purification.

Framed like this, citizens do appear in multiple roles: as providers of valuable feedback for the innovators that can help to improve the innovators work and the final products. But importantly, there is also a risk and the potential for them to get in “trouble”. This idea relates to discussions about how to integrate RRI principles and participatory approaches into the evaluation mechanisms at INNOVIRIS. Publics or citizens are understood here as potential as a hurdle or obstacle in need of being tamed. From this perspective, the main risk is that citizens (or evaluative citizen panels) might have the power to actually stop a project by evaluating it negatively. To solve this (fictional) issue our colleagues argue for

multiple engagements with citizens during a project's lifetime. In this way, citizens get a more complete picture of what is going on in the research projects and can make informed decisions.

The critical question becomes at what level of "maturity" can innovations be reasonably judged? What we see in this account then is a tension between upstream ambitions and the need to protect PhD students that can lead to a downstream push. How far up the stream can you safely go?

Another question that was raised in this pilot activity and that is relevant here relates to the question which elements of the research are relevant for deliberations in RRI – and more broadly -engagement settings.

"In the circular economy when you are doing some innovation, there are things that are quite technological. You have to design separation process that enables you to have to, for example, to (inc.) fraction that are separated because they cannot re-enter process of for the automotive industry if they are not separated, OK. And that's what is necessary actually is to transfer knowledge from the mining industry to the circular economy industry. So it's highly technological. And on that side citizen engagement is not interesting." (Int-12)

This opens up questions about the elements of an R&I project about which citizens and publics can legitimately deliberate and which areas should be off-limit. The overarching question then becomes who should be granted the authority to make these decisions. Who should define spaces and issues of legitimate engagement?

These discussions also have implications for how the different translations lead to distinct ideas about impact down the line. We will return to these questions in the comparative chapters. Before we do so, we want to briefly address another – to some extent overarching - pilot activity of the Brussels cluster, the so-called "Spheres protocols".

Chapter 7 – Comparison between the Three Clusters

Translation, care, and maintenance

In the previous chapters we spent time in Lombardy, Catalonia and in the Brussels-Capital region. We learned about the pilot projects of our TRANSFORM project partners working on participatory agenda setting and towards a push for deliberative democracy, in citizens science projects on the issues of waste collection and health, and on co-designing recommendations for regional development. We showed how all of these pilot projects are set in particular R&I ecosystems while also trying to influence or even re-shape these ecosystems. This is attempted through influencing both the processes as well as the content of regional innovation strategies, in particular their Smart Specialization Strategies (S3).

What we saw in the different regions was a great diversity of practices under the broader RRI umbrella. We opted for describing this diversity in terms of “translation”, a concept that allows us to trace both the symbolic and material elements of such transformations:

“Through the concept of translation, it is possible to emphasize not only the epistemic construction of political order, but also its material dimensions.” (Soneryd & Amelung, 2016, p. 172)

The way she uses translation the focus is on both (1) the shifts in meaning of concepts like participation, citizen, expert and so on, and (2) the making and re-making of links between different entities and agents thus directing attention to the organizational settings in which they are applied (or: with which they are co-produced).

Through this comparative perspective we also stress the ways in which certain translations become stabilized. Our premise here is that it is not at all arbitrary why certain versions of RRI are successful in a particular region while others are side-lined.

The activities of the TRANSFORM project clusters take place within certain organizational structures with their own histories and power structures. That are in addition designed carried out by a set of actors with their own preferences when it comes to the methods to apply and the issues to tackle. These are powerful “organizational carriers” (Soneryd, 2015)

that shape the translation of RRI in the regions. Looking for such carriers simply means acknowledging that RRI pilots don't start from scratch and do not take place in a vacuum. There have been initiatives before as there are most likely initiatives in parallel. Jason Chilvers and his colleagues in their work on UK energy system transitions in a similar way direct attention to what they call "wider spaces of participation" and "constitutional stabilities" (Chilvers et al., 2018).

Thus, in comparing the different cluster activities we will pay particular attention to such organizational carriers, the wider spaces of participation as well as the constitutional stabilities within which they take shape.

Part of this is also being mindful of the activities that go beyond the core project work and which focus on these particular institutional, organizational, and political contexts of the TRANSFORM pilots. We will do so by carving out the work that goes into caring for, nurturing and maintaining relationships that allow for the project activities to take place in the way they do. These ideas have been captured within the RRI discourse with the notion of "care" (Kjølberg & Strand, 2011). Stilgoe, Owen and Macnaghten (2013) explicitly relate this notion to the governance of science and technology:

"Responsible innovation means taking care of the future through collective stewardship of science and innovation in the present." (Stilgoe et al., 2013, p. 1570)

Responsibility here is presented as "taking care" of the future. This is supposed to happen by what Stilgoe et al. refer to as "collective stewardship" of science and innovation. This points to an idea of rethinking innovation governance along more democratic lines. Implicitly, one could argue, the call for making innovation governance systems "more" collective – read democratic – than it currently is. This in a sense is what the different clusters work towards in their own specific ways and also as one overarching Swafs14 project. In their respective translations of RRI into territorial R&I ecosystems the clusters find different forms of care, i.e. different ways of making research and innovation a more collective endeavor.

What is interesting to note here is also the particular temporality inherent in this framing of RRI. The way Stilgoe and his co-authors talk about RRI and care has at least two dimensions of temporality: first, they describe care as long-term engagement and in doing so contrast it to more short-term-oriented or one-off decision-making that follows a logic of choice. Second, adhering to a logic of care in R&I governance for them is about the timing of engagement with certain technoscientific issues, objects or fields.

At what point in the process of producing knowledge and developing innovations are different actors expected to become responsive to each other? This point is also a critique of predecessor notions and approaches like certain forms of Technology Assessment (TA) or work on the Ethical Legas and Social Implications/Aspects (ELSI/ELSA) of science and technology. The critique is that these approaches tend to intervene at the very end of these processes. In contrast, following a logic of care means early – or “upstream” - intervention and following that establishing an ongoing collaboration throughout the whole process. The goal of such a shift is “to emphasize caring responsiveness in technoscience” (Puig de la Bellacasa, 2011, p. 87).

On a more general level, the argument is to move beyond modes of governance that aim for prediction control as this is seen as part of the problem and contributing to the creation of the multiple crises we are facing today. (Guimarães Pereira, 2015) Instead, gearing the governance of innovation towards principles of care by consequence means to work towards “caring transformations to sustainability facilitate adaptation, ongoing tinkering, fine-tuning, and repair of processes and products by users situated in their settings.” (Arora et al., 2020, p. 248)

As such debates about RRI and care also relate to notions of maintenance that have entered the debates about science, innovation and the governance of R&I systems more recently. Usually used to describe very mundane practices of keeping things working, maintenance can also be thought of as an alternative mode of conceptualizing innovation. Thinking about innovation in terms of maintenance then means not fetishizing the new but instead focusing on caring for what is already there (Vinsel & Russell, 2020). As such, maintenance is positioned as an alternative to more traditional ideas of innovation (and its governance):

“In some ways, maintenance is the opposite of innovation. It is the practice of keeping daily life going, caring for the people and things that matter most to us, and ensuring that we preserve and sustain the inheritance of our collective pasts. It’s the overlooked, undercompensated work that keeps our roads safe, our companies productive, and our lives happy and secure.” (Vinsel & Russell, 2020, p. 14)

Similar to the idea of “taking care of the future” also maintenance has a decidedly temporal aspect. In the quote above, Vinsel and Russell talk about an “inheritance” and call for “preserving” and “sustaining” what is already there. While they talk about technologies and innovation, we believe that these notions are also a very useful lens to think about the

work going on in the different clusters. It is not only – or not even mainly – about creating something completely novel. Much rather the work in the clusters practices and enacts different forms of being innovative and responsible as they focus on - - building networks, nurturing relationships and in doing so slowly transforming cultures of responsibility in innovation governance. Work that is often neglected, invisible and marginalized.

Stressing the centrality of maintenance and care also provides us with a new way of thinking about the impact of the regional pilots and the TRANSFORM project overall. How is that so? Usually, when it comes to concrete RRI projects such as the ones funded by the EU SwafS programme, becoming responsive is mostly framed as "impacts" and "benefits". This can be seen as a direct consequence of the general rules of play, that is, the accountability measures, of EU funding schemes for research and innovation. However, "impacts" and "benefits" are notoriously hard to measure, in particular when it comes to something as abstract as transformative innovation governance. One possible explanation for this is that governance for transformation is not well suited for top-down, command and control intervention logics. RRI is better understood through network approaches and self-governance (Strand et al., 2015). This in turn means of course that the metaphor of "impact", understood as something which is the result of an external force hitting the system, is not very well chosen.

In this chapter we will take a comparative perspective of the three different clusters, look at the different translations of RRI we found and describe how they are co-shaped with the various R&I ecosystems. Building on that comparison we will describe the work of the clusters and their ambitions of "impact" from a care and maintenance perspective. This also means pointing towards some of the tensions that this kind of work creates in the different regional cluster when it comes to ambitions of long-term impacts and benefits as well as with aspirations of transformation.

What is "good engagement" for the different regions?

As we have shown in the previous chapters, the different clusters translate RRI in diverse ways. This concerns not the methodologies they apply, but also the purposes of this kind of work as well as the overarching ideas of what constitutes "good engagement".

In Lombardy, the focus remained mainly on working with policy- and decision-makers in the field of research and innovation.

“So, you can talk about and you can make responsible innovation if you work with people really involve and key in governing innovation, which means not only of course policy-makers but the people in charge of decision-making in governance and in the government, in the governments to govern research and innovation.”
(Int_05)

The position of FGB within the Lombardian innovation ecosystem gives it access to actors within Lombardy Region who are willing to participate in the pilots. This framing of RRI is thus closely tied to how the network is set up and to the long tradition of FGB working with the Region on issues of responsibility. This collaboration is also enshrined in the often-mentioned “Legge Regionale 23 novembre 2016, n. 29”, which states that to strengthen regional innovation and the competitiveness of the system a culture of responsible research and innovation needs to be established through the dissemination of and experimentation with innovative methods and processes. As we already mentioned in the chapter on the Lombardian cluster, this law also provides the legal basis for the “Forum for Research and Innovation”, for which FGB is formally recognized as a supporting body. There is thus what Chilvers, Pallett and Hargreaves refer to as “powerful systemic constitutional stabilities” (Chilvers et al., 2018) to the work FGB is doing in Lombardy.

Working with actors in key decision-making positions is thus one key criterion for good engagement. But there is more to this: good engagement also needs to be “real” in the accounts of our Lombardian colleagues.

This focus on working with policy- and decision-makers in order to achieve “real” engagement in the form of some actual consequences of the work, however, also means that the citizens and the subject positions available to them are different compared to the work in the other clusters. In the participatory agenda setting process that appear mainly as carriers of region-specific needs. The aim of addressing them via survey and focus-group methods is to give Lombardy Region more precise information about the needs of the different regions within Lombardy in order to improve their policies. Similarly, also in the citizens’ jury the participants are conceived of as carriers of a lived experience in the region and therefore as experts with regards to what needs to be improved. They are framed as “to ensure a diversity of voices, experiences and points of view”. As such they are distinguished from the more technical experts who participated in the event to inform the citizens about issues like Big Data and AI, open data and “some technological features of smart mobility”. The citizens then developed recommendations that were presented to Lombardy Region who “committed to taking citizens’ ideas and suggestions into account in its future actions

in the area of smart mobility and, should it not be possible to incorporate them (...), to explain the reasons for this.” While this certainly is state-of-the-art when it comes to citizens’ juries, it is a very particular way of engaging citizens which is closely tied to the ambition to provide something “real” and to showcase a methodology to regional administrative actors.

The foil of real engagement in the way our colleagues from Lombardy talk about their activities is “fake” engagement. Fake engagement is mainly characterized by not having any consequences whatsoever. And this is the second main principle of doing this kind of work in Lombardy: producing something that has a consequence or impact on the research and innovation policies in Lombardy. This impact, in the view of FGB, can be in terms of policy but also with regard to the very governance structures within Lombardy Region as a long-term ambition is to find ways of establishing a more permanent citizens’ assembly in the region.

Engagement in the Catalan cluster of TRANSFORM takes the form of citizen science but also efforts to mobilise the interest and opportunities for citizen science. The ethos of “real” engagement is also observed in this region. While it resembles that just described for Lombardy, a nuance is that the purpose is slightly different in Catalonia, and it is slightly different for different actors within the cluster. Above all, “real” refers to the issues chosen for the pilots – they should be real in the sense of addressing actual concerns in the region and for citizens, within the Catalan context of “improving society”. For the actors within the Catalan Generalitat with the responsibility to shape and implement its regional S3 plan, the RIS3CAT, improving society is a matter of deep transformation of its societal sectors including the R&I ecosystem.

The core value here is that of *transformation*, which can be said to be the system or structure counterpart of the main interest of the Open Systems Group at the University of Barcelona, which is to undertake and study social experimentation, again to improve society. The pilots being real is hence not the main goal in itself but a quality necessary in order for the pilots to have a value as showcases within the larger agenda of social transformation. The cluster leader, Science for Change, also indirectly aligns itself with this agenda, recognising the direct value of citizen science as a means to improve the quality of innovation – in the sense that solutions are imagined to be more relevant and more functional when those who experience the problems are part of the innovation process. However, we are constantly reminded that there is “more than that”, that significant added

value of citizen science exercises lies beyond and above the instrumental level, in the sense of improving transversal dialogue in all directions in society.

In the Brussels-Capital Region (BCR) cluster we observe several distinct yet related translations of RRI. Generally speaking, RRI is framed as some version of citizen participation or deliberative democracy. In the BCR cluster this takes the shape of policy co-design (in the Unsold Food pilot) and co-design of (technological) innovations of student-innovators from UC Louvain (AquaSens and Algorella). In addition to these pilot activities, the BCR cluster worked towards the development of the so-called “Spheres-protocol”, an overarching activity intended to analyse and support projects with regards to RRI.

These translations are also connected to different answers to the question “what constitutes ‘good’ engagement?” Good engagement in the BCR cluster centres around an ethos of “being of service”. Being of service here first and foremost means working with bottom-up initiatives and provide support with regards to emerging conflicts or in terms of support from public authorities. Crucially, engaging with initiatives that works on the issue of unsold food is intended to create conditions in which locally situated knowledge and lived experiences of food production and consumption systems can enter policy- and decision-making spheres. This idea of being of service thus carries connotations of community development but manages to weave in the administrative partner INNOVIRIS via their need to re-think evaluation criteria for the selection of regional innovation projects and to find ways of making such initiatives more “sustainable”. Be Participation – and this is a crucial difference to the Lombardy cluster – for these kinds of engagements exactly because it is not part of the extended governance structure yet still entertains connections to the policy realm.

There is another version of “being of service” that is enacted in the work of UC Louvain as well as in the overarching Spheres protocol. Here, the service is mainly aimed at researchers and intended to help them anticipate issues that they would not have otherwise recognized.

“And what is interesting is basically what we tried to also explain to the researcher is that you can develop a very nice innovation that will measure the quality of water but if you don’t pay attention to the perception that citizen have, you, they will maybe they will say okay, fine, I can test the quality but I will still use the bottled water.” (Int_10)

The work of this cluster in that sense followed a model of engagement that was in a sense very much led by the citizens. They had already organized into initiatives around the issue of unsold food bringing together themes of poverty and socio-economic inequality with questions of environmental protection and use of resources. Be Participations role was mainly one of providing the knowledge and experience with regard to co-design and multi-stakeholder engagement methods. The participants in the unsold food pilot thus were “used” to showcase the added-value of these methods to the public authority in the form of INNOVIRIS. At the same time, however, the engagement was still used to show some potential paths towards solving the issues and challenges. Our colleagues from Lombardy, however, were keen to point out that their mandate was not one of providing or elaborating solutions as they were only organizing piloting activities. In a similar manner also the work of UC Louvain was intended as engaging multiple stakeholders in the development of PhD student’s innovations while at the same time aiming to convince university managers to adapt the university’s doctoral education towards a more holistic view of innovation.

The actors that participate in these co-design workshops are framed by our colleagues as “disadvantaged publics”.

“So I thought well, you know one of the biggest challenges that we have in the activities we do is to involve disadvantaged publics and people who don’t feel entitled or interested for different reasons they don’t. So we thought okay, this could be a really nice collaboration.” (Int_09)

“Disadvantaged” as it is used here means that these actors are not part of a powerful elite that is able to shape policies and decisions. As such, they occupy different subject positions as participants in the other clusters, as they are the ones framing the problem. They have agency in the sense that they set-up an initiative independently from public authorities and already go into the engagement with their own issues and challenges. In addition, these are people who wouldn’t usually attend top-down focus groups.

The PhD-students from UC Louvain in contrast occupy a different subject position. They are framed as innovators who are in need of input from citizens with regard to the usability of their innovations as well as to potential ethical and social implications. As such they are sometimes also perceived as being in need of protection from the citizens, especially if they should be granted to mandate to cancel certain projects if they are seen to be dangerous.

Interestingly, in these conversations also the notion of “acceptance” came up on several occasions. And indeed, “acceptability” is indeed part of conceptualizations of RRI, as visible e.g. in this quote from von Schomberg (2012):

“Responsible Research and Innovation is a transparent, interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view to the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products (in order to allow a proper embedding of scientific and technological advances in our society)”

There are at least two ways in which one could think about acceptance in relation to RRI-work: on the one hand there is the more educationalist and awareness-raising type that aims for increasing the chances that citizens will not reject a technology or policy decision due to being informed about it. This is of the type “if only they knew more about X and understood it better, they could more easily accept X.” On the other hand one can think about acceptance or acceptability as creating processes that allow citizens to exert some actual influence on innovation pathways or certain decisions. This then would mean providing conditions under which research and innovation processes and their outcomes become in fact more “accept-able”. This version of course is closer to the core idea of RRI.

In the conversations we had about the cluster activities we addressed these nuances of the notion.

“I mean for the moment in Brussels you have a campaign about air pollution but what will be the, the perception of the people that have been employed in the in the campaign and the people that have not been employed in the campaign. Is there a difference. If there is a decision for example to say okay, we will limit that thing to increase the, the to increase the quality of air, what would be the acceptance in the two different groups.” (Int_11)

While this is close to the traditional idea of the problem of acceptance, the term also can be understood as the other of “social contestability”. Framed like this, Spheres turns into a “vehicle” for working with SME’s on “social contestability” issues. Similar to the challenges for the PhD student-innovators, the public here is framed as an obstacle for innovation or as an entity that will contest what innovators or researchers are doing.

“So they can focus on the technological aspect but they, they lack other competences that they could need in the lifecycle of, of the innovation at one

moment. Sometimes very early, sometimes a bit later. And strangely, they are working like they hope that succeeding on the technological part will solve each and every problem. And when we were asking them yes but what about social contestability because you will end up by doing that but it's not sure that your neighbour because some firm have just 50 metres are just at, sorry. Yes. 50 metres of their neighbours, so you have that not in my backyard problem and so on. What about your future social contestability They say well what is contestability. How do we manage that. And actually in the lifecycle of an innovation, it appears one, the problem appears. So they discover that you have Green Peace that is knocking at your door and saying you have to stop all the activity here because there is an environmental problem. And just replying "oh, we are a firm recycling waste" that, that is not solving the problem. So we discovered that we had to have a vehicle to a kind of what we called at that time one-stop shopping where they could find some competency that they don't have inside, OK and that they could use that very early in the innovation process, OK." (Int_12)

Here we see again a service logic attached to RRI work. However, this is slightly different from the one we talked about before. The objective of bottom-up engagement here means helping the innovator "to anticipate some questions about their impact on the environment, on the public health, equity."

After this comparative summary of the cluster's ideas about what constitutes "good engagement" we will now turn to the process of "piloting" as this overall framing of the TRANSFORM activities proved to be crucial to the actual translations of RRI in the regions.

Final Remarks – What about the Indicators?

Previous deliverables have discussed at length that the so-called MoRRI indicators, that were explicitly mentioned in the SwafS-14 calls and also in other parts of the latter SwafS work programme, are of little relevance in the context of individual projects such as TRANSFORM. This understanding, we believe, is close to a general consensus that has grown out of the SwafS ecosystem activities during the latter years. It is not only that MoRRI indicators are irrelevant for decisions; they are not even meaningful at the project level because most of them are defined at a higher (national) level of aggregation. Consequently, they are now very rarely used.

At the same time, our own Grant Agreement mentions a set of MoRRI indicators to which TRANSFORM might contribute. The wording of “contributing” to MoRRI indicators was not an invention of the TRANSFORM consortium; indeed, the exact same phrase was used in the SwafS-14 calls for proposal. Grammatically it makes little sense – one cannot really “contribute to an indicator” literally speaking. From the context of the SwafS work programme, however, there has been a general understanding in the SwafS ecosystem how this should be interpreted. It has been taken to mean that the actions should have outcomes and impacts that contribute to improving the states of affairs that the indicators were supposed to measure or at least be some kind of proxies for. In this way, it may make some sense to discuss “contributions” to these indicators, and it can be done quite readily, as follows:

TRANSFORM Task 7.4 should comment on contributions to “MoRRI indicators GE1, GE3, SLSE4, PE5, PE6, PE7, PE8 and GOV2 or their respective refinements or replacements as developed by SUPER_MoRRI”. Now, the SUPERMoRRI set is not yet ready, and we will comment on the mentioned MoRRI indicators.

Starting with the Gender Equality indicators GE1 and GE3, these refer to the share of RPOs and RFOs, respectively, with gender equality plans. The indicator is too coarse to detect gender quality impacts in TRANSFORM. Indeed, as one of our public authority partners noted, in their region, all RPOs have gender equality plans because this is mandatory by regulation. To what extent these plans are implemented and what level of ambition they have, is another matter, and a matter that cannot be grasped by the MoRRI GE set. If we

take the GE set as a proxy for the state of affairs of gender equality in the E&I ecosystem more generally, however, we may point to at least two contributions by TRANSFORM. First, in a very direct sense, the endometriosis pilot in Catalonia has contributed to gender equality by being a citizen science pilot that engaged and mobilised women with a much-ignored health condition and thereby improved the gender aspects of the content of research. Secondly, in a more indirect way, TRANSFORM may have made a contribution on gender equality by means of exemplary learning in the respective clusters, in that all three cluster leaders and the vast majority of persons-in-charge of project partners are female. From the WP7 perspective we suspect (although it is difficult to document) that this fact has had made a difference in terms of the highly dynamic and responsive governance of the project itself.

The SLSE4 indicator is a proxy for the presence of citizen science in RPOs. Taken more broadly, TRANSFORM has contributed to increase the presence and importance of citizen science in the Catalan R&I ecosystem, not only in traditional RPOs but more specifically by citizen science becoming introduced in the RIS3CAT2030 strategy.

PE5-PE8 are all indicators of public engagement. PE6 was dropped by the MoRRI consortium itself because of poor performance. PE5 is a measure of public engagement mechanisms in RPOs; PE7 embedment of PE in RFOs; and PE8 PE in evaluation criteria in research proposal evaluation. TRANSFORM has definitely contributed to the underlying state of affairs for PE5, PE7 and PE8. For instance, the pilots at UC Louvain introduced PE mechanisms in an RPO (PE5). All three clusters contributed to embedding PE in the regional S3 authorities (which can be taken to be “RFOs” in this context, thus contributing to PE7). And while the precise change of evaluation criteria did not take place during the lifetime of TRANSFORM, this was indeed one of the long-term ambitions shaping the work of the Brussels cluster (PE8).

Finally, GOV2 is a proxy for the presence of RRI-related governance mechanisms. Both in Lombardy and Catalonia, RRI was indeed embedded in practice and policy in the regional authorities during TRANSFORM (and then we already discussed above the methodological difficulties of causal attribution), and positive developments were also observed in the Brussels Capital Region.

The Grant Agreement also mentioned other possibly relevant indicator sets, such as those of the EC expert group on policy indicators for RRI (Strand et al. 2015) and of Wickson and Carew (2014). During the progress of the TRANSFORM project, these sets were replaced by the methodology of evaluative inquiry, as explained in deliverable D7.5. However, it may be

interesting to compare TRANSFORM contributions with the main process indicators that were recommended by the EC expert group. These are reproduced below (Strand et al. 2015, excerpt from Table 3.1):

	Process indicators
Public engagement	Number and degree of development of formal procedures for citizens' involvement (consensus conferences, referendum, etc.) Number of citizen science projects, discriminating from those supported by institutions and those that are created at grassroots level, by field
Gender equality	Percentage of research institutions that document specific actions that aim to change aspects of their organisational culture that reinforces gender bias
Science education	The inclusion of an initiative or requirement for RRI-related training in a research strategy/call/work programme, etc. (yes/no, percentage)
Open access	Inclusion of open science measures in research policies and calls for proposals
Ethics	Documented ELSI/ELSA project component and/or transdisciplinary component that addresses societal relevance and ethical acceptability (presence/frequency; qualitative descriptions; best practices)
Governance	Identification of formal and informal networks of R & I that promote RRI, at both the national and the EU level

Indeed, these qualitative process indicators for public engagement, gender equality, ethics and governance are better suited to characterize the positive contributions of TRANSFORM. The project developed and implemented formal procedures for citizens' involvement in all three regions; it worked on the gender bias of the organisational culture in one Catalan pilot; it introduced transdisciplinary components that addressed societal relevance in all three regions; and it most definitely worked on maintaining, nurturing, and fostering formal and informal networks that promote RRI in the three regions.

To sum up, in our assessment, TRANSFORM had significant positive outcomes and are likely to have had significant positive impact in line with the SwafS call and the Grant Agreement.

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